

Deep Learning for Human Activity Recognition: A Comprehensive Review of Architectures, Performance, and Challenges Across Five Sensory Datasets

Abeer FathAllah Brery¹, Ascensión Gallardo-Antolín², Mahmoud Fakhry³, Israel Gonzalez-Carrasco¹

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avenida de la Universidad, 30, Leganés, Madrid, 28911, Spain

²Department of Signal Theory and Communications
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Avenida de la Universidad, 30, Leganés, Madrid, 28911, Spain

³CEIEC, Universidad Francisco de Vitoria
Ctra.M-515 Pozuelo-Majadahonda Km.1, 800, Pozuelo de Alarcón, Madrid, 28223, Spain

Abstract

Human activity recognition (HAR) using sensor data allows the automatic detection of human behavior and actions in everyday environments. The development of scalable and privacy-preserving HAR systems is supported by the nonintrusive collection of time-series data using wearable devices and smartphone sensors. Advances in deep learning have further improved recognition accuracy, expanding the applications of HAR across domains, including healthcare and human-computer interaction. **Unlike existing surveys that primarily focus on architectural advancements, this study offers the first systematic review that places benchmark datasets at the forefront.** This study provides a comprehensive examination of various deep models used in HAR, assessing their relative advantages, limitations, and optimization strategies based on an extensive review of 226 studies. It also delves into the core aspects of HAR system design, including data preprocessing, feature extraction, evaluation metrics, and validation approaches. Through a systematic examination of 160 studies, we analyzed HAR systems built using deep models in terms of architecture, performance, and implementation challenges on five widely adopted benchmark datasets (USC-HAD, PAMAP2, WISDM, UCI-HAR, and OPPORTUNITY). To ensure a balanced comparison across the benchmarks, we analyzed 32 studies for each of the five datasets. **Our analysis reveals that hybrid models, particularly CNN-LSTM architectures, consistently achieve superior accuracy across benchmarks. Furthermore, the Adam optimizer and leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) validation protocols are identified as the most effective choices for robustness.** We conclude by identifying key obstacles, such as sensor noise, intersubject variability, and real-time processing constraints, and suggest future research directions to improve the robustness, generalizability, and efficiency of HAR systems.

Index terms— Comprehensive review, Human activity recognition, Mobile and wearable sensors, HAR datasets, Deep learning models

1 Introduction

Over the past decade, advances in microelectronics have enabled the development of smart devices capable of performing complex tasks. These devices can be integrated into the daily lives of individuals due to their compact size, high computing power, low cost, and low power consumption. Progress in ubiquitous computing and smart wearables has generated vast amounts of data on daily activities, bringing human activity recognition (HAR) to the forefront and enabling research initiatives to enhance individuals' quality of life. HAR has applications in several fields, including security, smart homes, and teleimmersion, where it aims to recognize actions in real-time and identify individual traits (e.g., identity, gender, and age) to enhance contextual awareness [1, 2]. This has significantly impacted the fitness, rehabilitation, emotion recognition, and education sectors. HAR systems are essential in healthcare and elderly care, enabling the detection of abnormal activities and timely interventions, thereby emphasizing the need for accurate and low-complexity models [3].

Human activities differ in terms of their nature, measurement methods, and ease of identification. These activities are categorized into body-level activities (e.g., walking and running), arm-level activities (e.g., shaking hands and brushing teeth), extremity-level activities (including lip reading and blinking),

Ambient Sensors	Wearable Sensors	Hybrid Sensors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Humidity sensors, temperature sensors, passive infrared sensors, etc. • Fixed to specific object or environment. • Smart homes, surveillance cameras, WIFI devices, etc. • Complete data acquired in a limited space, without weight or volume restrictions. • Risk of privacy invasion, restricted space, and expensive. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of sensors into wearable devices. • GPS sensors, accelerometers, gyroscopes, heart rate sensors, etc. • Smartphones, smartwatches, etc. • Unrestricted space, high flexibility, low cost, and small size. • High-precision component design, low wearer comfort, production difficulty. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combine Ambient & wearable sensors. • Temperature and humidity sensors, accelerometers, gyroscopes, etc. • Integration of WIFI devices, smart homes, surveillance cameras, etc. with smartwatches, smartphones, etc. • Multiple sensors for joint data acquisition. • Complexity with high cost.

Figure 1: Sensors of HAR.

vital sign-level activities (e.g., snoring and coughing), and multilevel activities (including swimming and cleaning), with research distributions of 21%, 8%, 42%, 5%, and 24%, respectively, [4]. Human activities are categorized into simple and complex atomic activities. Simple actions, such as walking, can be detected using a single accelerometer sensor, whereas complex actions, such as house cleaning, involve multiple overlapping actions and require multimodal sensor data [5]. HAR also includes basic and transitional movements, with limited research on transitions such as ‘walking to standing’ owing to their short duration and low frequency [6]. Human activity recognition using smartphones and wearable sensors (UCI-HAPT dataset) [7] is the only dataset specifically designed to capture postural transitions, such as walking-to-standing and standing-to-sitting transitions. Analyzing these transitions can improve activity recognition because they represent infrequent but essential activities. Recognition becomes more difficult as activity granularity decreases, and challenges increase for activities at finer levels.

The type of sensory data used has a profound effect on the methodologies, algorithms, architectures, and strategies employed [8–10]. CCTV cameras (52%) and mobile phone sensors (26%) are the most common data sources for HAR. Other sources, such as Kinect (1%), smartphone cameras (1%), camera images (4%), social media images (3%), wearable body sensors (8%), and YouTube videos (5%), were used less frequently [11]. HAR is classified into two main categories based on the type of sensory data: (a) vision-based, which uses images and videos to capture human activities, and (b) sensor-based, which relies on data from wearable devices and object-tagging techniques. With the rise of inertial measurement unit technology for microelectromechanical systems (MEMS IMU) in smartphones and wearables, HAR is shifting from image-based to sensor-based approaches [12]. In addition, sensor-based methods use data from wearable, ambient, or object sensors to effectively address computational efficiency and privacy issues. Sensor-based HAR involves identifying activities from raw sensor readings and is commonly framed as a multivariate time-series classification problem [13]. Time-series data contain distinct patterns specific to each activity and individual [14], and the interpretation and readability of such raw data present major challenges in HAR [15]. Figure 1 provides an overview of the different sensors used for HAR.

Although wearable sensors offer higher accuracy, they are less convenient than non-wearable sensors, which are easy to use but have low accuracy [16]. Despite this trade-off, wearable sensors are critical for elderly care and assisted living because they provide reliable data on daily activities [17]. Advances in wearable technologies have led to the development of smart sensors that can efficiently capture physiological data with low power and processing requirements [18]. A diverse array of smart devices, including smartphones, smartwatches, rings, glasses, gloves, shoes, and necklaces, offers faster and more intuitive use. However, concerns regarding data security and confidentiality persist in remote monitoring applications [19]. Nevertheless, wearable sensors are preferred because of their flexibility and precision.

Collecting sufficient ground-truth labelled training data for realistic HAR benchmarking is expensive. Dataset creation involves preparing recording sessions, defining activity categories, creating a recording environment, and configuring sensor systems [20]. For example, conducting recording sessions requires drafting recording protocols, selecting human participants, and ensuring their privacy and confidentiality. The process also involves annotating the recordings, addressing faulty data, documenting them, and publishing them. Moreover, the selection of an appropriate dataset depends on metrics such as the number of subjects, activities, and sensors, which influence its suitability for specific research objectives. Careful consideration of these factors ensures the reliability of the dataset, leading to meaningful conclusions and valuable contributions.

Several research entities have produced HAR datasets using wearable sensors for various applications, most of which are publicly accessible. The University of California Riverside time-series classification (UCR-TSC) archive is a compilation of datasets derived from various sensing modalities [21]. Initially launched with 16 datasets, the UCR-TSC archive has grown substantially, reaching 85 in 2015 and 128 in

Figure 2: Processing flow of HAR systems.

October 2018. Recently, researchers from the University of East Anglia collaborated with UCR to curate a novel dataset spanning nine HAR categories. These categories include racket sports, handwriting, basic motions, cricket, epilepsy, ERing, UWaveGesture Library, NATOPS, and Libras [22]. In [23], the authors reviewed more than 150 sensor-based datasets specifically designed for HAR using installed sensors. Although many studies have investigated the reviewed datasets, published manuscripts are often not robust and lack open access for broader research.

Developing accurate HAR systems is challenging because of variations in human activities (context, duration, and intensity) and sensors (types, placements, and brands) across frequency and sensitivity ranges [24]. Research has shown that chest-mounted sensors outperform those on the hand or ankle, particularly in lower-extremity exoskeletons [25]. Using multiple sensors at different positions significantly increases the accuracy of complex activities; three sensors are optimal [26]. The accuracy of HAR systems in real-world environments tends to be lower than that in controlled laboratory environments [27]. The block diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the processing flow of HAR systems. The process begins with data acquisition using sensors and devices that capture daily activity data, followed by data preprocessing, such as enhancement, filtering, and segmentation. Distinctive features are extracted during the feature extraction and selection phases. Machine learning (ML) or deep learning (DL) models are trained and evaluated using the selected features to predict activities. The classification performance of the model is measured and analyzed to fine-tune the model through hyperparameter optimization. The final model is deployed in practical scenarios, such as behavior monitoring and healthcare diagnostics. **Despite the proliferation of deep learning models for HAR, there remains a significant gap in understanding how these architectures perform across standardized benchmarks. Existing surveys often focus on architectural taxonomy without sufficiently analyzing dataset-specific biases or performance variability. The motivation for this review is to bridge this gap by providing practitioners with evidence-based guidelines for model selection that account for dataset characteristics rather than relying solely on reported accuracy.**

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents existing surveys in the literature. The contributions of this study are described in detail in Section 3. Data preprocessing and feature extraction are discussed in Sections 4 and 5, followed by deep learning models in Section 6. Sections 7 and 8 detail existing optimizers and validation protocols, respectively. Section 9 presents the measurement metrics used to evaluate model performance. Section 10 discusses the datasets and previous studies that used them. Section 11 presents a discussion of the key findings, and Section 12 summarizes the challenges and future research directions. The conclusions of this study are outlined in Section 13.

2 Related Existing Surveys

In recent years, several survey studies have explored HAR. Some studies have delved into the intricate aspects of HAR methodologies and various deep learning techniques; however, few have focused on datasets. Ongoing advances in sensor technologies and data processing methods, combined with the increasing variety of human activities, require regular updates to ensure that HAR systems remain up-to-date. This refines deep models, enhancing their accuracy and applicability in real-world settings.

The study in [28] explored 28 deep models, focusing on accuracy as a key metric across 11 randomly selected sensor- and vision-based datasets; however, it lacked direct comparisons of datasets. Similarly, [29] reviewed eight machine learning and nine deep learning techniques and discussed their applications and challenges; however, they reported only incomplete accuracy and general descriptions of five datasets. The authors of [19] classified existing HAR studies into sensor type, application domain, DL methodology,

and challenges. In addition, they highlighted key datasets, six deep learning architectures, and relevant studies, along with the accuracies achieved on some datasets.

Studies on deep learning for HAR tasks based on video and sensor datasets were examined in [30], along with descriptions of several datasets. Although this study discusses preprocessing, challenges, and limitations of HAR research, it does not include any performance metric comparisons. The study in [31] presented a systematic review of sensor-based datasets in HAR using scientometrics, analyzing publication variables (year, database, type, quartile, and origin) and dataset characteristics (occupation, annotation, approach, segmentation, representation, feature selection, and balancing). However, it reviewed no more than six papers for some key datasets. Challenges in HAR related to open datasets were investigated in [32], which included a comprehensive review of the literature from January 2016 to February 2023, along with a questionnaire for researchers experienced with open HAR datasets.

In [33], a survey analyzed various deep models and proposed guidelines for selecting suitable approaches based on factors such as sensor modalities, activities, training, and real-time requirements. It provides valuable insights and visual aids for building case-specific deep learning pipelines. [4] provided a systematic review of HAR for mobile devices, detailing the rationales, main components, and challenges. In [34], the authors conducted a comparative study on feature extraction using conventional handcrafted methods. It focuses on mobile and wearable sensors, covering generative techniques such as deep belief networks (DBN), deep Boltzmann machines (DBM), and sparse coding; discriminative models such as convolutional neural networks (CNN) and recurrent neural networks (RNN); and hybrid architectures.

The study in [35] investigates HAR systems based on smartphones and wearable sensors, categorizing the approaches into conventional methods, long short-term memory (LSTM) models, and hybrid techniques, while highlighting their characteristics, advantages, limitations, and commonly used benchmark datasets. The review in [36] introduced multimodality in sensory data and highlighted public datasets for various challenging tasks. It presents a new taxonomy for structuring deep methods, explores specialized deep learning models, and discusses open issues. The survey in [21] provides a tutorial introduction to HAR using on-body inertial sensors, detailing the activity recognition chain framework, its components, and related studies. It offers best practices and concludes with an educational example of hand gesture recognition.

3 New Contributions

In contrast to existing surveys on DL for HAR, this study presents the first systematic review to place benchmark datasets at the forefront. Although current literature often focuses on architectural taxonomy, it frequently lacks the comparisons necessary for practical deployment. This review addresses this gap by using benchmark datasets as a core criterion and facilitating clearer comparisons that reduce inefficient resource allocation and "decision paralysis" for system designers. Specifically, we conducted a comprehensive examination of recent DL-based HAR systems, emphasizing studies that utilized five of the most widely adopted benchmark datasets in the field. By adopting dataset use as a core review criterion, this study facilitates a clearer comparison of methods and highlights dataset-specific trends, limitations, and opportunities for future research. **The primary relevance of this work is to distill complex architectural choices into evidence-based guidelines, transforming academic metrics into engineering specifications for real-world applications.** The main contributions of this review are as follows:

- **Taxonomy of HAR systems:** A structured overview of HAR, encompassing sensor modalities, annotated activities, and real-world applications, contextualized through contemporary literature.
- **Systematic literature synthesis:** A rigorous consolidation of 224 studies, balancing state-of-the-art research to ensure temporal relevance and methodological diversity. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the annual publications.
- **Comparative analysis of DL architectures:** An examination of recent DL models, detailing their topologies, performance trade-offs, and domain-specific adaptations. The discussion extends to the associated preprocessing pipelines, feature extraction methods, evaluation metrics, validation protocols, and optimization algorithms.
- **Dataset-centric benchmarking:** A critical comparison of five benchmark datasets—USC-HAD, PAMAP2, WISDM, UCI-HAR, and OPPORTUNITY—addressing their scalability, annotation granularity, and biases. Guidelines for dataset selection and curation in HAR pipelines are proposed to ensure alignment with specific application constraints.

Figure 3: The distribution of 226 referenced publications over years.

Figure 4: Search protocol.

- **In-depth model-dataset analysis:** A focused evaluation of recent and highly cited studies, dissecting architectural choices, hyperparameter sensitivity, and performance variability across datasets. The innovations, limitations, and reproducibility gaps in this study are discussed.
- **Open challenges and future directions:** Identification of unresolved issues in wearable-sensor-based HAR, including label noise, cross-domain generalization, and computational efficiency, with actionable recommendations for bridging the gap between laboratory benchmarks and robust system deployment.

3.1 Systematic literature search strategy

To ensure a comprehensive, transparent, and reproducible review process, we adhered to a systematic search protocol aligned with the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (i.e., PRISMA) guidelines. Recognizing the interdisciplinary nature of HAR, which spans biomedical engineering, computer science, and pervasive computing, the search was conducted across five major academic databases: PubMed, Embase, IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. This multi-database approach was strategically selected to maximize the coverage of both biomedical literature (via PubMed and Embase) and technical engineering publications (via IEEE Xplore and Web of Science), thereby minimizing selection bias and ensuring a robust representation of state-of-the-art methodologies. To ensure methodological stringency, the search was limited to peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings. The search strategy employed a structured combination of keywords using Boolean operators to capture relevant studies across three concept groups: activity, methodological, and dataset identifiers. Specifically, the search string was formulated as follows: ("human activity recognition" OR "human activity detection" OR "HAR" OR "HAD") AND ("deep learning" OR "neural networks") AND ("USC-HAD" OR "PAMAP2" OR "WISDM" OR "UCI-HAR" OR "OPPORTUNITY"). To ensure the inclusive retrieval of relevant literature, search terms were applied to *all fields* within each article (e.g., title, abstract, keywords, and full text) rather than limiting the search to titles or abstracts alone, thereby minimizing the risk of omitting pertinent studies that may not have explicitly mentioned the targeted keywords in prominent sections. This rigorous methodology initially identified a broad corpus of publications, which were subsequently screened and analyzed to yield a final balanced selection of **160 unique studies** (32 per dataset) included in the qualitative synthesis. Figure 4 shows a block diagram of the search protocol.

4 Data Preprocessing

Sensor data exhibit local dependency, whereas human activity signals possess hierarchical and translation-invariant characteristics that reflect dynamic system information [37]. Data preprocessing in HAR is crucial for enhancing the quality and relevance of sensor data. The initial step typically involves denoising methods, such as moving average smoothing or triangle filtering, to eliminate unwanted noise and outliers that can impair model performance. Missing sensor readings are often addressed by discarding incomplete data samples or using interpolation methods based on nearby temporal or spatial measurements. The additional preprocessing strategies discussed in the literature [38] vary according to the sensor modalities and targeted activities. Data standardization is also a common step applied to normalize feature distributions to ensure compatibility with machine learning algorithms that assume data with zero mean and unit variance. Moreover, techniques such as data segmentation, windowing, and feature scaling are employed to structure the data for optimal learning. Effective preprocessing improves model accuracy and contributes to greater generalizability across different users and environments.

Data segmentation, the process of extracting data segments corresponding to human activities, is essential for preserving the context of the activities. This strategy, such as sliding windows, peak point detection, valley point detection, and thresholding, helps break down raw sensor data into meaningful segments [39, 40]. Sliding window methods divide data into fixed-size segments with or without overlap [41]. Its straightforward implementation and minimal preprocessing requirements make it ideal for dividing sensor time series into continuous, fixed-length, and overlapping samples. A fixed-size sliding window is commonly used; however, it lacks awareness of the underlying time-series data type and structure [21, 42]. The importance of window size underscores the fact that a window that is too small lacks information continuity, leading to misclassification. In contrast, an excessively large window encompasses multiple activities, leading to a multiclass window problem [43] and classification errors [44, 45]. Typically, window sizes ranging from 500 to 5000 ms are considered appropriate [44].

Various methods have been proposed [46, 47] to transform time-series data into a modified space, simplifying the feature extraction process by minimizing the impact of residual noise or random variations. Exploring transformations in time-series sensor data yields diverse features across different spaces; however, relying solely on a single transformed space may limit the feature extraction performance [48]. Integrating effective features from diverse spaces through joint optimization remains a challenge for optimal activity recognition. In addition, it is crucial to apply appropriate data transformation methods based on the type of sensor data. For motion sensor data, transformations include coordinate system adjustments, integration, discrete wavelet transform, and fast Fourier transform (FFT). Acoustic signal processing uses methods such as short-time Fourier transform (STFT), Doppler effect analysis, and mel-frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCCs) analysis. The transformation of image data includes color

space conversion, edge detection, skin segmentation, Hough transformation, and six-segment rectangular filtering. These techniques aim to refine the data for subsequent HAR tasks.

5 Feature Extraction

Research on HAR using wearable devices faces several challenges, including optimal device placement, mood-related movement variations, and difficulties in data collection, particularly for elderly or disabled users. Fixed device positions can limit mobility and complicate HAR studies [49]. To achieve user-independent position detection, researchers have focused on extracting invariant features and normalizing data based on sensor positions. However, predicting activities with limited features is difficult because of the complexity of human movement, which requires additional characteristics to achieve better accuracy [50]. Feature extraction, whether manual or automatic, is crucial for identifying essential features from sensor data and reducing classification errors and computational complexity.

Despite requiring domain-specific knowledge, handcrafted features are effective for classification tasks because of their simple setup [51]. They allow feature extraction from both the time and frequency domains with low computational complexity [52]. These features fall into three main categories: time-domain (e.g., mean, standard deviation, zero-crossing rate, duration, and coefficients derived from discrete transforms), frequency-domain (e.g., maximum value, bandwidth, dominant frequency, and spectral entropy), and spatial domain (e.g., width, orientation, eccentricity, center of an ellipse, and spatial correlation). Although frequency-domain methods achieve high accuracy, they have a higher computational complexity ($O(N \log N)$) than time-domain methods ($O(N)$) [53]. Handcrafted extraction is often task-specific and impractical, particularly when the data structure is uncertain owing to a lack of experience.

Automated features derived from deep learning models, such as CNNs and LSTMs, capture complex patterns in data and reflect both low- and high-level features. These models identify sustained motion, thereby enabling the recognition of prolonged and continuous activities. They extract comprehensive attributes from the input data to achieve a holistic understanding of the activity. In addition, high-level motion features are captured that encapsulate overall movement patterns and dynamics, thereby providing a robust representation of the activities being performed [4].

A combination of handcrafted and automated features [54] and multitasking strategies [55] has been proposed to enhance feature representation. Furthermore, to address the challenge of extracting features from multimodal sensor data, deep learning employs various strategies, such as feature fusion at different levels, attention mechanisms, data augmentation with different modal data, and graph convolutional network-based dynamic intersensor correlation learning [4].

Feature extraction is often time-consuming and generates a limited number of features from datasets [56]. It can also produce irrelevant or redundant features, increasing the feature space and affecting classification accuracy [57]. To mitigate this issue, feature selection techniques that can identify more relevant features should be used. These methods, such as filtering and wrapper approaches, are NP-hard problems aimed at improving performance and reducing time and space requirements. Filter methods quickly rank and remove less important features according to a predefined metric, whereas wrapper methods, although more accurate, use classifiers to evaluate feature subsets [57].

6 Deep Neural Networks

The pioneering HAR system introduced in [58] uses five dual-axis wearable accelerometers and traditional machine learning classifiers to identify 20 activities, achieving an accuracy of 84%. Traditional machine learning models trained on curated data in controlled settings often struggle to handle diverse, heterogeneously distributed data streams [59]. Recently, deep learning has surpassed traditional methods by providing automatic feature extraction and reducing the need for complex preprocessing and expert knowledge [60]. This shift has increased the recognition accuracy in HAR research [61]. Figure 5 shows the basic structures of the different DL models developed for HAR-related tasks.

Various DL models have been developed using different internal constructions, optimization methods, and applications. When selecting a model, factors such as problem complexity, computational resources, training time requirements, data quality, dataset size, availability, and annotation size should be carefully considered [19]. For example, a fully connected network (FCN) is a deep network in which each neuron in a layer is connected to every neuron in the subsequent layer. Although FCNs are typically less effective than specialized networks, they are versatile and often serve as the final layers in convolutional

Figure 5: Deep learning models used in HAR-related tasks.

architectures. Table 1 provides a concise overview of the various DL networks used in HAR, including their applications, advantages, disadvantages, and challenges.

6.1 Mathematical formulations of core architectures

To provide a rigorous foundation for the reviewed architectures, we outline the mathematical background of the most prevalent models used in the 160 studies included in this review.

6.1.1 Convolutional neural networks (CNN)

The core operation of a CNN is convolution, which extracts local features from input data while preserving spatial or temporal relationships. For a 1D input signal $x \in \mathbb{R}^T$ and kernel $w \in \mathbb{R}^k$, the feature map h at position i is computed as indicated in Eq. (1):

$$h_i = f \left(\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} w_j \cdot x_{i+j} + b \right). \quad (1)$$

Here, $f(\cdot)$ is a nonlinear activation function (e.g., ReLU: $f(z) = \max(0, z)$), k is the kernel size, and b is the bias. For multisensor HAR data, 2D convolutions can capture both temporal and intersensor

Table 1: Deep learning models for HAR.

Approach	Suitable Use	Advantage	Disadvantage	Challenges
CNN [62, 63]	Hierarchical feature extraction, and indoor and outdoor HAR	High accuracy, scale invariance, and adaptable architecture	Prone to overfitting, and struggle with complex or dynamic activities	Data variability and demands a substantial amount of annotated data
Capsule Networks [64, 65]	Complex activity recognition	Robust to spatial transformations	Limited interpretability	Training instability
RNN [66]	Time series analysis to encode temporal features	Capture dependencies and flexible to data size	Vulnerable to vanishing gradients	Long training time
LSTM [66]	Modeling long-term dependency in time series data	Handle long sequences and flexible data size adaptation	Limited capacity and ignores spatial features	Requires large datasets and need to enhance poor parallel processing
GRU [67]	Sequential data and long-term dependencies	Minimal parameters, and fast convergence	Limited memory capacity	Difficulty in fine-tuning
Attention [68]	Sequential data processing	Focus on relevant information to learn relations	Computationally intensive	Attention drift
Ensemble [69]	Model combination	Improved robustness	Increased complexity	Model diversity
TCNs [70]	Time series forecasting	Parallelization	Fixed-length input	Limited context modeling
GCNs [71, 72]	Graph-based data processing	Captures spatial relationships	Complexity in graph construction	Scalability
DBN [73]	Learning low-dimensional features and less common	Captures hierarchical features	Slow convergence and laborious training	Parameter tuning and training with deeper networks
Autoencoders [74]	Extract low-dimensional representations	Dimensionality reduction and noise suppression	Limited interpretability of pertinent characteristics	Model complexity and parameters to adjust during training
Transformers [13]	Long-range dependencies and sequential data processing	Parallel processing to capture contextual information	High computational cost and memory requirements	Ensuring scalability and efficiency for large datasets and sensitivity to hyperparameters
GANs [19]	Data augmentation and robust capacity for learning	Generates synthetic data to reduce data demands	Mode collapse and hard to train	Training instability
Deep Reinforcement [75]	Dynamic environments	Learns from experience	Sample inefficiency and human participation are critical issues	Reward design and time-intensive training difficulties
TL [76]	Domain adaptation	Use pre-trained models	Requires large dataset	Domain shift

dependencies following in Eq. (2):

$$H_{i,j} = f \left(\sum_{m=0}^{k_h-1} \sum_{n=0}^{k_w-1} W_{m,n} \cdot X_{i+m,j+n} + B \right), \quad (2)$$

where H is the output feature map, W is the 2D kernel, and X is the input tensor. Pooling operations (e.g., max-pooling) reduce spatial dimensions and enhance translation invariance, as indicated in Eq. (3):

$$P_{i,j} = \max_{m,n \in \mathcal{R}} H_{i+m,j+n}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{R} defines the pooling region. As shown in Eq. (1), 1D convolution operations capture local dependencies over time but overlook interchannel dependencies in multisensor data, whereas 2D operations (Eq. (2)) can capture both temporal and spatial dependencies in sensor data but are not optimal for memory-constrained mobile devices due to their parameter-intensive nature [62, 63]. Although CNNs have excelled in HAR, they suffer from drawbacks, such as information loss in the pooling layer (Eq. (3)) and poor generalization owing to translation invariance. Unlike traditional CNNs that use single neurons, capsule networks (CapsNets) are composed of multiple neurons [64] and have demonstrated superiority over CNN for HAR [65].

6.1.2 Recurrent neural networks (RNN) and variants

RNNs process sequential data by maintaining a hidden state h_t that captures temporal dependencies. The standard RNN update is computed as indicated in Eq. (4):

$$h_t = f(W_{xh}x_t + W_{hh}h_{t-1} + b_h), \quad y_t = g(W_{hy}h_t + b_y), \quad (4)$$

where W_{xh} , W_{hh} , and W_{hy} are weight matrices, b_h and b_y are biases, and $f(\cdot)$, $g(\cdot)$ are activation functions. However, standard RNNs suffer from vanishing gradients, which limit their ability to model long-term dependencies.

Long short-term memory (LSTM) LSTM units mitigate the vanishing gradient problem using gating mechanisms. The forget gate f_t , input gate i_t , cell candidate \tilde{c}_t , cell state c_t , and output gate o_t are defined as:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f), \quad (5)$$

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i), \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{c}_t = \tanh(W_c \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c), \quad (7)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tilde{c}_t, \quad (8)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o), \quad (9)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t), \quad (10)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid function, \odot denotes element-wise multiplication, and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ represents concatenation. Long short-term memory was designed to address the limitations of recurrent neural networks, which are commonly used for processing sequential data. LSTM incorporates memory blocks with cells in hidden layers, which enables long-term information modeling compared to RNN (Eqs. (5)–(10)) [66].

Gated recurrent unit (GRU) GRU simplifies LSTM by combining the forget and input gates into an update gate, z_t , and introducing a reset gate, r_t .

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_z), \quad (11)$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_r), \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W_h \cdot [r_t \odot h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_h), \quad (13)$$

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) \odot h_{t-1} + z_t \odot \tilde{h}_t. \quad (14)$$

GRU integrates gating mechanisms to retain relevant past information while selectively removing less important details and preserving the long-term context (Eqs. (11)–(14)) [67]. This dual approach enables the model to capture sequences in both forward and backward directions simultaneously [77]. This dual approach enables the model to capture sequences in both forward and backward directions simultaneously [78]. It captures information from both past and future contexts, thereby enhancing its ability to comprehend complex data sequences.

6.1.3 Attention mechanisms

Attention mechanisms allow models to focus on relevant parts of the input sequence. For a sequence of hidden states $\{h_1, \dots, h_T\}$, the attention weight α_t for time step t is computed as

$$e_t = v^\top \tanh(W_a h_t + b_a), \quad \alpha_t = \frac{\exp(e_t)}{\sum_{k=1}^T \exp(e_k)}, \quad (15)$$

where W_a , v , and b_a are learnable parameters. The context vector c is then expressed as

$$c = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t. \quad (16)$$

The introduction of attention mechanisms in LSTMs and GRUs improves their accuracy by focusing on the relevant parts of the input data and mitigating noise (Eqs. (15)–(16)) [68]. Self-attention extends this by computing attention over the same sequence, thereby enabling the model to capture long-range dependencies without recurrence [13].

6.1.4 Transformer architecture

Transformers rely entirely on attention mechanisms to process input data. The multi-head attention module computes H parallel attention heads as follows:

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_H)W^O, \quad (17)$$

where each head is:

$$\text{head}_i = \text{Attention}(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V, \quad (18)$$

where Q , K , V represent queries, keys, and values, respectively, and d_k is the dimension of the keys. Positional encodings are added to the input embeddings to preserve the sequence order. Transformers overcome the parallel computation limitations of RNNs and effectively handle long-term dependencies in deep learning models (Eqs. (17)–(18)) [13].

6.1.5 Capsule networks

Capsule networks (CapsNets) represent features as vectors (capsules) to encode pose information. The coupling coefficient c_{ij} between capsule i in layer l and capsule j in layer $l + 1$ is computed via dynamic routing:

$$c_{ij} = \frac{\exp(b_{ij})}{\sum_k \exp(b_{ik})}, \quad b_{ij} \leftarrow b_{ij} + u_{j|i} \cdot v_j, \quad (19)$$

where b_{ij} is the prior log probability, $u_{j|i}$ is the prediction vector and v_j is the output of capsule j . This enables CapsNets to better model hierarchical spatial relationships than CNNs (Eq. (19)) [64, 65].

6.2 Model selection considerations for HAR

Researchers have developed hybrid models that combine series and parallel configurations of specialized networks to address complex prognostic challenges [79, 80]. Recent HAR research has focused on hybrid models that use CNNs to extract spatial features and RNNs to model temporal dependencies [68, 81]. Ensemble methods and hybrid techniques are prominent in DL [69]. In sensor-based HAR, an underexplored but valuable approach involves using information fusion to create an ensemble of classifiers that integrates decisions from multiple models for greater robustness [82]. However, their effectiveness depends on the diversity of the constituent classifiers. If all components tend to mispredict the same patterns or exhibit similar prediction traits, the overall utility of the ensemble method is significantly reduced [50].

The concept of temporal convolutional networks (TCNs) was introduced to effectively analyze long-range time-series data [70]. One of the defining features of TCNs is the use of causal convolutions and a dilation factor in their causal convolutions to capture long-term dependencies more efficiently without requiring a deep network architecture design. Graph convolutional networks (GCNs) are multilayered convolutional networks with powerful deep learning architectures designed to operate on graph-structured data, allowing them to effectively capture the relationships and dependencies between nodes in a graph [71]. GCNs leverage node relationships through convolution operations and enable the propagation of information across neighboring nodes, thereby facilitating tasks such as node classification, link prediction, and graph-level tasks with high accuracy and efficiency.

Deep generative models, such as deep belief networks and autoencoders, enable unsupervised learning by capturing complex data representations. Deep belief networks (DBNs) are composed of multiple fully connected layers formed by stacked restricted Boltzmann machines (RBMs) that capture increasingly abstract features through their hierarchical layers [73]. Autoencoders are fully connected deep models with various internal structures [74]. Convolutional autoencoders process structured grid-like data and leverage convolutional layers for feature extraction and spatial preservation. Recurrent autoencoders are suitable for sequential data and incorporate recurrent layers to capture temporal dependencies. Both models are effective for feature extraction and pattern discovery, and their resistance to overfitting makes them ideal for using unlabeled data [36].

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) are a class of deep generative models that produce new samples by learning from real data. They were initially developed to generate fake images that resemble those in the training dataset. GANs consist of two networks, the generator and discriminator, which are optimized to find a Nash equilibrium; however, this is not guaranteed in theory [19]. In HAR, GANs are used as a semi-supervised learning approach to enhance model performance by leveraging unlabeled or partially labeled data to learn representations that generalize effectively to unseen data distributions [83]. Subsequently, GANs have demonstrated the capability of generating realistic synthetic sensor data.

Deep learning for HAR often struggles with the need for extensive annotated data, especially ground truth labels, which are costly and time-consuming to obtain from inertial sensors, such as accelerometers or gyroscopes [84]. In addition, with small datasets, deep learning may not outperform traditional machine learning methods. Several strategies have been explored to address these issues. One such strategy is reinforcement learning, which involves an agent learning optimal decision-making policies by interacting with the environment [85]. The agent acts, receives rewards, and aims to maximize long-term rewards by learning from this interaction. Deep reinforcement learning combines reinforcement learning with deep learning to enable agents to make decisions in complex, high-dimensional spaces [75]. Another well-known

Table 2: Summary of main optimization algorithms in HAR.

Optimizer	Mechanism	Advantages	Disadvantages	Usage in Reviewed Studies
SGD [88]	Stochastic Gradient Descent (Updates using a single random example or a small batch)	Simple, good generalization	Slow convergence, sensitive to learning rate	Less frequent, often with Momentum
RMSprop [90]	Adaptive learning rate (Extends GD and Adagrad)	Time-efficient execution	Hyperparameter sensitive	Moderate usage
Adam [92]	Adaptive moment estimation (Exponentially decaying averages of past and squared gradients)	Stable gradient descent, efficient for large datasets	Generalization issues in some cases	Most frequent
Adadelata [89]	Adaptive learning rate (Variant of Adagrad)	No manual learning rate tuning, robust to noisy gradients	Can be slow to converge	Limited usage
AdamW/Adamax [93]	Decoupled weight decay (AdamW) / Infinity norm (Adamax)	Reliable training, robust	Variant specific complexities	Emerging usage

approach is transfer learning, in which new tasks are learned with few labels using a large set of labels from a related task [76]. In addition, active learning (AL), which aims to minimize annotation costs by selecting samples for labeling while improving model performance, has been proposed for HAR [86, 87].

7 Optimizers

Training neural networks requires an appropriate optimization algorithm. Common choices include stochastic gradient descent (SGD), adaptive gradient (Adagrad), adaptive learning rate (Adadelata), root mean square propagation (RMSprop), and adaptive moment (Adam) methods. Figure 6 shows the developmental genealogy of the optimizers most commonly used in the literature. Table 2 presents a comparison of the main optimizers.

SGD is an optimization variant of gradient descent (GD) that is used to improve the computational efficiency. Unlike GD, which uses the entire dataset for each iteration, SGD updates the model parameters using a single random example or small batch, thereby introducing randomness into the training process. This reduces the computational cost per iteration, thereby making it more efficient for large datasets. Adagrad is an extension of SGD that adds a self-adaptive learning rate to each parameter of the objective function [88]. Adadelata is a variant of Adagrad that dynamically eliminates manual learning-rate tuning and is robust to noisy gradients, different model architectures, and hyperparameter selection [89].

RMSprop is an adaptive learning rate optimizer that extends GD and Adagrad to reduce the computational effort required to train neural networks. The RMSprop optimizer is frequently used because of its time-efficient execution [90]. Adam combines the benefits of Adagrad and RMSprop by maintaining exponentially decaying averages of past and squared gradients, similar to the momentum method [91]. Adam is efficient for large datasets and optimal, like RMSprop, for small networks and short training durations, whereas Adagrad and Adadelata perform better with larger models [92].

Other Adam variants, such as AdamW and Adamax, use decoupled weight decay and infinity norm for reliable training, respectively [93]. HN-Adam enhances convergence by adjusting the step size and blending Adam and AMSGrad [94]. ND-Adam bridges the gap between Adam and SGD with L_2 weight for gradient direction preservation [95].

Regarding HAR, several studies have compared the performance of various optimizers for this task; however, there is no general agreement on the best one because it depends on the architecture, dataset, and other factors. In [39], SGD, Adagrad, Adadelata, Adam, and RMSprop were evaluated, with results favoring Adam because of its stable gradient descent curve and superior fitting. Despite using a variety of optimizers, including batch GD, SGD, Momentum, Adadelata, RMSprop, and Adam [79], and Adam, Adagrad, SGD, and RMSprop in another study [24], the researchers consistently identified Adam as the most effective choice in their work. The studies in [63, 96] employed SGD, Adagrad, Adamax, Adam, and RMSprop optimizers to evaluate their effects on model convergence. Researchers often favor SGD with momentum over Adam because of the generalization issues observed in models trained using Adam [97].

Figure 6: Developmental genealogy and dependency of the most commonly used optimizers.

8 Validation Protocols

In HAR tasks, a crucial procedure involves partitioning the data into training, validation, and testing sets. Various methodologies have been employed in HAR using wearable sensor data, including K-fold cross-validation (CV), leave-one-subject-out (LOSO), leave-one-trial-out (LOTO), hold-out, and leave-one-sample-out (also known as leave-one-out). Traditionally, K-fold CV (for example, with $K = 10$) and LOSO protocols are widely favored, whereas hold-out and leave-one-sample-out protocols are used in fewer instances. LOSO and LOTO protocols are deemed the most suitable methodologies to report results in sensor-based HAR [98]. Although it is more time-consuming owing to its repetition with different subjects in the test set, LOSO-CV offers a more realistic estimate of HAR accuracy for new users than CV or hold-out approaches [99]. Extensive LOSO validation experiments have shown enhanced robustness to noise and subject-specific variability in body-worn sensor signals [100]. The alternative splitting technique involves a percent split (PS by data), where the dataset is divided according to a percentage (e.g., 70-30%, 80-20%), and a subject split (SS), where a certain percentage or number of subjects is allocated for testing/validation, and the remaining subjects are used for training [101, 102]. Manual selection (MS) allows the splitting of HAR problems based on a subject or data, allowing validation by specific subjects or data percentages [44, 89].

9 Performance Metrics

The effectiveness of HAR systems is evaluated by calculating four essential metrics. True positives (TP) indicate instances in which a specific activity is accurately identified. False negatives (FN) represent instances in which the model erroneously categorizes a particular activity as part of other activities. False positives (FP) denote cases in which the model mistakenly categorizes other activities as belonging to a specific activity. True negatives (TN) indicate instances in which other activities are correctly identified. Additional measures can be calculated to better understand system performance.

- **Precision** is the ratio between the number of correctly classified positive samples and the total number of samples classified as positive [103].

$$\text{Precision (PPV)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \quad (20)$$

- **Recall or sensitivity** is the ratio between the number of positive samples correctly classified as

positive and the total number of positive samples [103].

$$\text{Recall (TPR)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (21)$$

- **Accuracy** is calculated as the ratio between the number of correct predictions and the total number of predictions [28].

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}. \quad (22)$$

- **Specificity** is the ratio between the number of negative samples correctly classified as negative and the total number of negative samples [39].

$$\text{Specificity (TNR)} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}. \quad (23)$$

- **F1-score or F1-Measure** is a harmonic mean of recall and precision. This metric was introduced to combine both metrics into a single metric [39].

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Recall} \times \text{Precision}}{\text{Recall} + \text{Precision}} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}. \quad (24)$$

- **Informedness (BM)**: is a measure of how informed a system is about positives and negatives [104].

$$\text{BM} = \text{TPR} + \text{TNR} - 1. \quad (25)$$

- **Markedness (MK)**: is a measure of the trustworthiness of positive and negative predictions of the HAR system [104].

$$\text{MK} = \text{PPV} + \text{NPV} - 1, \quad \text{where} \quad \text{NPV} = \frac{TN}{TN + FN}. \quad (26)$$

- **Mean average accuracy (MAA)** is the average recall overall activities and is defined for the total number of activities (E) [105].

$$\text{MAA} = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^E \left[\frac{TP}{TP+FN} \right]_e}{E}. \quad (27)$$

- **ROC curve**: The receiver operating characteristic curve shows the trade-off between TP and FP rates at different thresholds [19]. The area under the curve (AUC) measures model performance, with a higher AUC (near 1) indicating greater sensitivity and an AUC below 0.5 indicating poor accuracy.
- **The confusion matrix** is a key metric for evaluating model performance [98]. It provides a detailed breakdown of TP, TN, FP, and FN values. This enables a nuanced evaluation of the model's ability to accurately identify and classify various human activities, thereby guiding refinements to improve accuracy in practical applications.

10 Datasets

Figure 7 illustrates most datasets in HAR, along with those under consideration, using a word cloud, where font sizes indicate the usage frequency of each dataset [32]. The selected datasets primarily include activities of daily living and various postures. When selecting an appropriate HAR dataset, researchers should prioritize datasets with comprehensive documentation, including published studies, sensor details, data collection procedures, and data formats. It is also important to examine key data characteristics such as timestamps, noise levels, and missing values. Researchers should define relevant keywords and search terms aligned with their domain-specific problem, establish clear research objectives, and allocate adequate resources for data processing. Additionally, ensuring data quality and exploring available libraries for data cleaning and preprocessing are essential steps.

Figure 7: Widely used datasets in HAR.

Table 3 presents the specifications and limitations of the five selected datasets, including those with the highest and lowest accuracy levels, as determined from the studies included in this review. The datasets reviewed include the University of Southern California–human activity detection (USC-HAD) dataset [106], physical activity monitoring (PAMAP2) dataset [107], wireless sensor data mining (WISDM) dataset [108], University of California Irvine–human activity recognition (UCI-HAR) dataset [109], and OPPORTUNITY dataset, which used wearable, object, and ambient sensors for HAR [110, 111]. The following subsections and Tables 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 explain and summarize studies and research that used these datasets. *In these tables, all numbers representing accuracy are in percentages.* Any number accompanied by the following symbols represents specific F1-score terms: (*) for the standard F1 score, (§) for weighted F1, (†) for average F1, (‡) for macro F1, and (†‡) for average macro F1. The following abbreviations are used in these tables: RS: raw signal, S: softmax, S: subject, D: dense, MP: maxPool, DO: dropout, FC: fully connected, BN: batch normalization, P: parallel, Concat.: concatenation, att: attention, Seq.: sequential, Res: residual, GAP: global average pooling, Fu: fusion, A: ADL, R: Run, conv: convolutional, F: flatten, TT: train/test, TVT: train/validation/test, Opt: optimizers, VP: validation protocol.

10.1 HAR systems evaluated using USC-HAD dataset

This section presents an overview of recent advances in different architectures evaluated on the USC-HAD dataset, including dynamic and deformable CNNs, hybrid models, and multiscale frameworks. Studies incorporating attention mechanisms, transformers, and autoencoders have demonstrated their effectiveness in optimizing feature representations. For further details, refer to Table 4.

In [42], a heterogeneous convolution approach divides the kernels in a CNN into two groups: one that recalibrates the other. Dynamic CNN introduces dynamic kernels with attention that adapt weights [115], and deep convolution constructs an ensemble stream by employing late fusion [90]. The authors introduced a deformable CNN by creating flexible heat maps [40] and integrating linear transformations and grouped convolutions within a CNN [86]. The authors explored CNNs with different filter activations in [104] and performed a comparative analysis of different DL architectures that confirmed the superiority of CNNs in [116]. Multiple transformations of time-series data combined with deep CNNs were presented in [48]. The model developed in [117] integrates LSTMs and deep RNNs into one architecture, whereas the model developed in [15] combines CNNs and LSTMs. In [68], the authors introduced multiscale hierarchical CNNs that incorporate adaptive feature fusion and dynamic channel selection based on LSTMs. The hybrid model proposed in [118] consists of a CNN with a squeeze-and-excitation block, parallel LSTM, and GRU layers. In [119], a deep triplet network was introduced using dual-attention LSTMs with a hierarchical triplet loss. The model developed by [120] comprises CNNs, self-attention blocks, and global temporal attention blocks. The studies in [56, 121, 122] used self-attention mechanisms incorporated into a hybrid model of CNN and LSTM. In [100], the authors proposed a hierarchical self-

Table 3: Details of five HAR datasets considered in this review.

A: Accelerometer, G: Gyroscope, M: Magnetometer, OB: Object Sensor AS: Ambient sensors, HR: Heart rate sensor, S: Subjects, TT: Train/Test, W: Walking, Sit: Sitting, Sta: Standing, J: Jumping.

Datasets	USC-HAD [106] 2012	PAMAP2 [107] 2012	UCI-HAR [109] 2012	WISDM [108] 2012	Opportunity [111] 2012
Repository	Wearable sensor-based	UCI Machine-Learning	UCI Machine-Learning	Smartphone Sensor-Based	UCI Machine-Learning
Scenario	In laboratory ADL data	In laboratory ADL data	In laboratory ADL data	Out-lab real-world ADL	In laboratory non-ADL data
# Citation	733	1715	3314	3812	936+1013
Subjects	14	9	30	36	4
Activities	12	12	6	6	21
Activities name	Sit, Sta, W(right, left, forward), up/down stairs, J, running forward, sleeping, elevator(up, down)	Sit, Sta, W, Nordic W, rope J, lying, running, cycling, up/down stairs, vacuum cleaning, ironing	Sit, Sat, W, lying down, up/down stairs	Sit, Sta, W, jogging, up/down stairs	Sit, Sta, W, lying, open/close (fridge, door(1,2), drawer(1,2,3), dishwasher), drink from cup, toggle switch, clean table
Devices	Motion node	3 IMU Units & 1 HR monitor	Smartphone	Android Phone & Smartwatch	Body-worn object & AS
# Devices	1	4	1	1	20
Sensors(S)	A, G, M	A, G, M, HR	A, G	A	A, G, M, OB, AS
Sensor Position	Waist, Thigh, Arm, Chest	Wrist, Ankle, Hand, Arm, Thigh	Waist, Lower Back	Right pant pocket	Upper/Lower Arm, Wrist, Back, Shoe, Hip
Examples(TT)	7,600/3,200	255,481/63,871	11,988/2,997	770,000/250,000	55,576/13,894
FE	Raw Sensor Data, Statistical Features				
Sample rate	100 (Hz)	100 (Hz)	50 (Hz)	20 (Hz)	32 (Hz)
Instances	14,000+	2,844,000+	10,299	1,098,207	4,063,560
Application	Healthcare, ambient intelligence, Sports	HAR, Fitness Tracking	Health Monitoring	Activity Monitoring	Lifestyle Monitoring & HAR, Context Recognition
Limitations	Data taken from one sensor location & elevator signal taken from only one sensor	S1,2,5,8: the only sufficient samples for all activities & Not representative of reality	Limited sensor positions, basic activities	Single Accelerometer, Limited sampling rate, pocket-only placement	Imbalanced Dataset2010
Challenges	Multimodal	Multimodal	Multimodal	Class Imbalance	Multimodal
Highest Accuracy	[104] 99.61 CNN	[60] 99.64 CNN-RNN	[112] 99.92 DCNN-LSTM	[113] 99.83 CNN-BiGRU-Attention	[114] 99.79 Transformer

attention model that integrates data from different sensors using an autoencoder architecture. A fusion network consisting of a lightweight attention mechanism and hierarchical CNNs was developed in [71], and attention fusion within a hybrid network of a GRU and depth-separable CNN was presented in [123].

A two-stream transformer network with self-attention mechanisms was presented in [124]. Meanwhile, [125] introduced a binarized vision transformer (Bi-DeepViT) for classifying wavelet spectrograms by evaluating three binarization methods. A CNN and temporal correlation transformer with attention were integrated into one architecture in [63]. In [13], the authors introduced a deep CNN with a deep reverse transformer-based attention mechanism using an LSTM deconvolutional decoder. A time convolution network with an attention mechanism was evaluated in [126]. The model introduced in [127] combines MobileNet-v2 with BiLSTM, and the model developed in [128] demonstrated that channel equalization enhances network generalization. A multi-class autoencoder with a support vector description of the data was presented in [129]. The authors of [130] proposed eliminating preprocessing steps using low-dimensional features extracted by an adversarial autoencoder. In [131], the authors proposed a dynamic weight optimization and smoothness constraint strategy within a shallow ResNet framework supplemented by MLP blocks. In [87] a one-class support vector machine was trained to dynamically identify new activities and iteratively extend training sets. The study by [132] introduced a transformer model and MLP modules with static and dynamic activity aggregation strategies.

Some studies treat elevator-up and elevator-down activities as a single activity because of the limitations of using only acceleration sensors to detect ascent and descent in an elevator moving at a constant speed [48] [130], which improves accuracy. Although most researchers use raw sensor data as input for DL models, some have used a wavelet spectrogram [125] and 2D matrix representation (i.e., Gramian angular field, recurrence plotting, and wavelet scattering transform (WST)) [48].

Table 4: USC-HAD Dataset.

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[42]	RS→CNN→(HC+BN+Relu)→CNN→FC+S	TVT:7:1:2 /Adam	Heterogeneous convolution (HC) adjusts the field within filter groups	HC can be involved in networks such as residual networks without modifications	CNN+HC:90.67, Res+HC:93.49
[115]	RS→3 seq. dynCNN→FC+S	TT 80:20 /Adam	Dynamically learns kernels using attention	High performance but computationally costly	95.13
[90]	RS→multi-dynCNN (2seq.Conv+Fu+FC+S) /sensor→fusion for all sensors →FC+S	LOTO, LOSO /RM- Sprop	Extract patterns from each sensor at multiple scales, and fuse features from multiple sensors	Dependency on multiple sensors separately may limit its applicability	DE:88.49, MDE: Multi-modal+DE: 90.08
[40]	RS→3seq.DFC→F+FC+S	TVT:7:1:2 /Adam	Deformable convolutional (DFC) modulate feature amplitudes	DFC is an inner mechanism, and its impact is not fully revealed	CNN+DFC: 95.36, Res+DFC:97.35
[86]	RS→3:6(CNN or ResNet+grouped conv.)→FC+S	TT 70:30	Lightweight convolution with transformations	Low computational and memory overhead	Grouped /+CNN: 94.26 /+Res:94.26
[104]	RS→CNN with filter activation →FC+S	TVT:7:1:2 /Adam	CNNs with filter activation to reactivate existing invalid filters	Can be integrated into CNNs because it operates at the layer level	prune: 97.38, noise: 99.61, active: 99.54
[116]	RS→(3Conv2D 3LSTM 3biLSTM 3GRU 1:6 RBM DBN)→FC+S	a random 5-CV /-	Conducted an extensive analysis of various deep architectures	The analysis was performed based on performance, speed, and memory requirements using ten public datasets	CNN:92.97, GRU:93.03, bi/LSTM:92.58/ 92.1,DBN:82.13
[48]	RS→WST→2P(Conv1D+Conv2D)→2FC+S	5-CV /Adam	Multi-stage training approach	Complexity in managing and tuning multiple CNN models	2Stage:98.57, M-Stage 99.02
[117]	RS→FE→LSTM→fusion →BGWO→FC+S	TT 70:30 /Adam	Fusion of features with binary grey wolf	Handcrafted FE is crucial but challenging	98.6
[15]	RS→2CNN+F→LSTM+Relu→FC+S	TVT:7:1:2 /-	1DCNN-LSTM with class weight adjustment	Simple architecture with early stopping	window-wise: 55*,LOSO:68*
[68]	RS→FE→Fu(HMconv,2P(MP+Conv+Relu+Conv),2Conv)→LSTM→FC+S	TVT: 80:10:10 /Adam	Hierarchical multiscale adaptive CNN-LSTM (HMA Conv-LSTM)	Computational complexity at distinguishing actions with subtle differences	53 [‡]
[118]	RS→BN+3(Conv+SE+BN+Relu+MP)+SE→LSTM+GRU→F+S	TT 80:20 /Adam	Deep CNN, LSTM, and GRU with an SE block	Multiple layers and components may require high computational resources	98.56
[119]	RS→Sensor att→LSTM →Temporal att→FC+S	kNN: k=7 /Adam	Triplet loss functions with triplet sampling	Computational complexity of triplet network attentions	53.5*
[120]	RS→modality att→Conv1D →self-att→GTA→FC+S	test:S13,14, LOSO/Adam	Self-attention generates high-dimension features	Capture different sensor modality and placement value	67 ^{†‡} 55 [‡] (test subject)
[56]	RS→Conv1D→LSTM+encoder→self-att→S	5-CV, LOTO /Adam	A self-attention mechanism to a hybrid network	Effective across diverse sampling and scalable to many sensors over long periods	90.88
[121]	RS→Concat.((Conv+PE+ self-att),(Conv+self-att) →Conv+Relu→FC+S	LOSO / Adam	Two CSNet and TCCSNet architectures with position encoding	Requires optimizing the handling of diverse data modalities and improve robustness	CSNet: 87.72, TCCSNet: 88.32
[122]	RS→4Conv2D→2LSTM →self-att+S	LOTO /Adam	Hybrid CNN, LSTM with self-attention	Requires fine-tuning and large features	90.91
[100]	RS→Hierarchical self-att encoder→D+S	hold out, LOSO/Adam	Hierarchical self attention autoencoder	Robust with complex implementation	68 [‡]
[71]	RS→CBR+(GAP+Conv+sigmoid)+CBR→GCN+MP→FC+S	TT 80:20 /-	STFNet: lightweight spatio-temporal fusion	Low memory overhead but challenges with consistent fusion	92.59
[123]	RS→Pipe(GRU+MP), CNN,(DSC+BN+Relu),CNN seq layers+AP→FC+S	TT 80:20 /Adam	Dual pipeline with novel spatio-temporal fusion attention	Improved feature fusion	97.67
[63]	RS→CNN→Transformer→ Attention →FC →S	TVT:rest:S-11,12:S-13,14/Adam	Hybrid CNN and transformer	Robust to weak features though using higher-level feature correlations	Transformer:84, ConvTransformer: 86
[124]	RS→Conv1D→multi-att +feed-forward→global-att →D+S	LOSO-CV /Adam	Two-stream transformer to capture sensor/time and time/sensor features	Inefficient in handling short-duration activities with similar sensor signals	57 [‡]
[13]	RS→Concat.(3Seq.(CNN +2Re att))→FC+S	K =10 CV /Adam	Transformer with self-calibrated attention	Computational costs with non-optimal static learning	95.14*
[126]	RS→Fu(3P-TCN)→self-att →GAP+DO+S	TT 80:20 /-	TCN-attention using knowledge distillation	Knowledge distillation reduces model parameters	96.32
[127]	RS→CNN-MobileNetv2 →CGO→BiLSTM→FC+S	TT 80:20/ CGO	CNN and MobileNetv2 with CGO tuning	Limiting applicability on very resource-constrained devices	93.1
[128]	RS→3CNN→CE→FC+S	TVT:7:1:2 /Adam	CNN channel equalization (CE)	Prevents channel collapse into CNNs without overhead	CNN/: 97.21, +CE:99.17
[129]	unlabeled pool→AE-AL→selected samples→annotate →labeled samples	5,891 test of 9,824 /Adam	AE-AL autoencoder and active learning with support vector description	Model and time complexity	90.79
[130]	RS→AEE→1DCNN+1D AP →F →FC+S	TVT:6:2:2 /-	CNN and adversarial auto-encoder (AEE)	Distinguishes both general and similar activities	99.10
[131]	RS→3X shallow ResNet →AvgP→MLP→S	TT 80:20 /Adam	Dynamic weight with smoothness constraint	Addresses class imbalance with spatial encoding	97.67
[87]	RS→FE(time-Freq.)→Dynamic AL of OCSVM	TT 80:20/ AL policy	Active learning (AL) by new activity discovery	Adaptive with low annotation costs	91.70
[132]	RS→Transformer →MLP→MLP→S	TT 64:16:20/-	A transformer with conditional transition	The model is sensitive to dynamic activities than static	89*

Continued on next page

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[125]	RS → CWT → DeepViT transformer → S	TT 70:30/Lion	a binarized vision transformer (Bi-DeepViT)	Low computational cost of transformers via binarization	90.96

10.2 HAR systems evaluated using PAMAP2 dataset

This section highlights recent advances in various models evaluated on the PAMAP2 dataset, including perception networks, hybrid architectures, and approaches that incorporate attention and ensemble techniques. Studies leveraging transformers, adversarial learning, and GNNs are also discussed, demonstrating their effectiveness in optimizing deep learning. Further details are provided in Table 5.

The perception network introduced in [89] utilizes vertically stacked motion signals and CNNs, whereas in [133], the authors optimized CNN architectures by gradually evolving simple architectures through layer addition. A CNN with conditionally parameterized convolution was presented in [134], and another CNN with local loss integration was described in [135]. The study in [136] introduced two CNNs differing in depth and width using multibranch topologies and structured parametrization. A lightweight deep model integrating CNNs with a fusion operator was developed in [137]. In [25], the authors evaluated the performance of a CNN model and a hybrid CNN-LSTM model that achieved similar accuracies. The model in [138] combines CNN and LSTM with fuzzy softmax, whereas the model in [139] consists of LSTM, followed by CNNs. A deep BiLSTM model incorporating post-processing windowing and voting was introduced in [140]. In [5], the authors introduced deep CNNs with a fusion strategy followed by LSTM. The data fusion introduced in [141] uses CNN, LSTM, and CNN-LSTM models with early and late integration of features, and [142] uses CNN-BiLSTM with multi-feature fusion with sequential forward selection. In [3], the authors merged CNNs and GRUs into one architecture, whereas in [2], the authors combined CNNs and BiGRUs into a hybrid model. In [143], the authors developed a hybrid model with three variations: CNN, CNN-LSTM, and CNN-GRU. A study by [144] compared the performance of five models: CNN, LSTM, BLSTM, MLP, and SVM.

The model developed in [145] uses a CNN with channel and temporal attention submodules. Residual attention blocks were employed for multimodal fusion within a deep CNN [146], and an inception module and a CNN block attention module were combined with a GRU [147]. CNN and GRU were integrated into one network using an attention mechanism and multimodal data fusion [81]. BiLSTM was integrated with a residual block in [12], whereas BiGRU and a multilevel residual block with attention were combined into a single architecture in [148]. A network ensemble of two CNNs and a single RNN was developed in [60], and a network ensemble of multiple autoencoders, each trained to reconstruct sensor measurements from distinct classes, was introduced in [149].

Generative neural networks (GNNs) have been incorporated with a multi-head attention mechanism [150]. A multi-head attention transformer model addresses the intra-class variability introduced in [151]. A transformer-based adversarial learning framework was introduced in [152], which used self-knowledge distillation for cross-domain data distribution alignment. Another model employs data enhancement to extract hybrid features and feed them into transformers [16]. In [153], the authors explored various local prediction loss functions in residual networks. The system developed in [154] employs Euler angle extraction and an MLP to jointly refine the placement and enhance identification accuracy. A study by [155] applied a multisource data fusion approach using an MLP.

All studies used raw sensor data as input for the DL models, except those in [81, 154] which employed a 2D spectrogram using the short-time Fourier transform (STFT); those in [150] which used graph data; those in [139], which focused on the discrete wavelet transform (DWT); and those in [146], which used a 2D scalogram through the continuous wavelet transform (CWT).

Table 5: PAMAP2 Dataset.

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[89]	RS → 2Seq.(Conv1D+MP) → (Conv2D+GAP) → D+S	LOSO/ adadelata	Vertically stacks data with late fusion	Confuses standing with sitting activities	88.56
[133]	RS → adjustable 1D CNN → FC	TVT:(S1:5): S6:S7/Adam	Auto design optimal 1DCNN by adding layers	Reduces the manual selection of hyperparameters	0.9432
[134]	RS → n(CondConv+BN+Relu) → CondConv+S	TT 70:30/ Adam	CNN with conditional parametrization	No compromising computation cost	94.01
[135]	RS → n Seq.(CNN+Local loss block) → FC+S	TT 80:20/ Adam	Layer-wise CNN with local loss functions	Low memory requirement with good generalization	92.97

Continued on next page

Table 5 – continued from previous page					
Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[136]	RS→3Seq.CNN→reparameter CNN→FC+S	TT 80:20/ Adam	Dynamic with structural reparameterization	Efficient with good integration capabilities	92.97
[137]	RS→2Seq. 1DCNN+Fu→GAP→MLP→S	TT 70:30/ Adam	Lightweight AReNet with cascaded training	Low computational complexity with optimal identification	99.24
[25]	RS→2Seq. 1DCNN→4LSTM→1DCNN→FC+S	TT 70:30/ Adam	CNN and hybrid CNN-LSTM	Validated performance using only accelerometer data	CNN and Hybrid: 90
[138]	RS→preprocessing→CNN→LSTM→Fsm	LOSO CV /-	Hybrid CNN-LSTM with fuzzy softmax (Fsm)	Notable improvements in robustness and performance	97
[139]	RS→DWT→LSTM→1DCNN+DO+S	TT 80:20/ Adam	Hybrid LSTM-Conv1D Model	A single layer may limit the depth of the feature extraction	86.85
[140]	RS→BiLSTM→LSTM+FC+D+BN+DO→2Seq.(D+BN+DO)→D+S	TT 70:30 /-	multilayer BiLSTM with novel post-processing windowing and voting	Improved recognition rate depending on dataset parameters and window size	93.41*
[5]	RS→Conv subNetworks→depth concat.→Conv1D+2LSTM→D+S	LOSO/ RMSprop	Subnetwork of CNNs-LSTM for each sensor	Difficulty to differentiate CHAs from similar SHAs and to model temporal structures	83.6*
[141]	RS→2Seq.(Conv1D/Sensor)→Conv1D→2Seq.LSTM→D+S	TVT:rest: S6:S5/RMS-prop,Adam	Two fusions: position-based early and late sensors	Considers wearable sensor data not capturing all aspects of complex activities	CNN-LSTM (LF/EF): 92.49/89.23
[142]	RS→2(Conv+MP)→SFSANW→BiLSTM→FC+S	-/-	CNN-BiLSTM with multi-fusion and SFSANW features selection	Comprehensive data representation with a fixed window	CNN-BiLSTM :90.65./+MFF: 91.64
[3]	RS→2seq.(CNN+F)→(GRU+DO+GRU+BN)→D+S	TT 8:2/ Adam	ICGNet: a hybrid model of CNN and GRU	Few parameters with low computational costs	97.64
[2]	RS→Conv1D+MP+F→RNN+DO→FC+S	10-CV / Adam	hybrid models combining CNN with RNN	Focuses only on wrist-worn sensors	85.5*
[143]	RS→1DCNN→(LSTM or GRU)→F+S	TVT: 70:20:10 /Adam	Three hybrid models (1D-CNN, CNN-LSTM, CNN-GRU)	Suffers from intra-class variability and class imbalance	CNN/+ :96.23, GRU:96.59, LSTM:97.28
[144]	RS→3Seq.(Conv+MP)→F+FC+S	TT 70:30/-	Proposing CNN with comparison to LSTM and BiLSTM	Conducted over 3000 experiments to analyze suitability and performance	CNN:91, LSTM:85.86, BLSTM:89.52
[145]	RS→Fu 3Seq.((2Seq.CBR+att),(Conv+BN+AvgP))→FC+S	TT rest: S5,6/Adam	Channel and temporal dual-attention	Visualize attention weights with high effectiveness of weakly labeled data	CNN+att:92.45, ResNet+att: 93.16
[146]	RS→CWT→Conv→Residual att→Conv+MP→RAB→MP+FC+S	TVT: 70:20:10/ Adam	CWT with DCNN for multimodal data with scale estimation	Its effectiveness in limited modalities cases may be less optimal	DWCNN:0.94, /noCWT:0.91, /noRAB:0.92
[147]	RS→(GRU+AM+GRU)→(2I+MP)→(DO+CBAM)→I→GAP+DO+S	TVT: rest:rest: S5 /-	GRU and inception with convolutional block attention module (CBAM)	Low computational overhead	90.31*
[81]	RS→FFT→Conv+att→GRU+att→S	LOSO/ Rmsprop	CNN and GRU with attention	Multimodal fusion with Enhanced GRU capability	89.3*
[12]	RS→Res+DO+F→BiLSTM+DO→D+S	TT 70:30/ Adam	Combining ResNet with BiLSTM	Few parameters and computational efficiency	97.15
[148]	RS→Concat.((n+1)P 1DCNN, (n+1)P Res.)→Adaptive AvgP→BiGRU+AM→2FC+S	TT rest: S5,6/Adam	Combining multilevel CNN, residuals, and BiGRU with attention	Allows for the integration or disconnection of sensors	CNN+ BiGRU:90.37, MultiResAtt: 93.19
[60]	RS→(Conv+MP+Conv+DO)→(RNN+Relu+F+DO)→RNN+FC	TVT: 80:10:10/ Adam	Ensemble of CNNs and RNNs	Robust against class imbalance and good generalization without overfitting	99.64
[149]	RS→hand-crafted FE→training→ensemble AES	LOSO/ Adam	Ensemble of auto-encoders (AEs)	Adaptable, with each AE having different layers	91.00
[150]	RS→2(graph att+Norm+LeakyRelu)→GAP+S	TT 70:30 /-	MhaGNN: GNNs and multi-head attention	Fast convergence of graphical data for all activities	MhaGNN: 96.74
[152]	RS→concat.(CNN/Sensor)→spatial-att→2AvgP+FC→3Discriminat+2FC+S	LOSO/ Adam	Transformer with max mean regularization and knowledge distillation	Computational costs with enhanced stability and preventing biases in generalization	83.04
[16]	RS→FE→nSeq.(Multihead att+Norm+Feed-Forward+Norm)→FC	TT 80:20 /-	Transformer encoder with fusion of low-level and high-level features	Low training time with limited computational resources	98.2
[153]	RS→3 residual blocks, Local loss blocks→FC+S	TT 80:20 /Adam	Block-wise training with local loss functions	Low memory requirements	Predsim+ CNN:92.58, Res:93.95
[154]	FFT→MLP+GAM→Transformer→FC+S	10-CV /-	Group attention integrated with MLP	Euler angles with refinement might have confusion struggle	93.96
[155]	RS→MLP→S	5-fold CV/-	Multisource feature fusion with MLP	Captures complex dependencies but generalizes poorly	98.54
[151]	RS→Multi-head attention block→S	TV 80:20/Adam	A multi-head attention transformer	Captures subtle differences between activity classes	95.42

10.3 HAR systems evaluated using WISDM dataset

This section explores hybrid models that combine CNNs with LSTMs, GRUs, and BiLSTMs, which were evaluated using the WISDM dataset. Models incorporating attention mechanisms, fusion strategies, and ensemble methods are also reviewed. Furthermore, the application of capsule networks and edge-computing-assisted frameworks highlights the advancements in optimizing the computational efficiency

and adaptability of these models. Further details are provided in Table 6.

HARCNN, introduced in [156], comprises ten CNN blocks and uses hierarchical feature fusion. Hybrid models were built based on CNNs and LSTMs [39, 157], CNNs and BiLSTMs [77], and CNN, LSTM, and BiLSTM [158] to extract spatiotemporal features and capture long-term dependencies. In [159], the authors introduced a lightweight model that incorporates CNN, RNN, and LSTM networks. Other models combine CNNs and GRUs [160, 161], while others integrate multichannel CNN and GRU to improve feature extraction and learn temporal relationships through fusion methods [162]. BiGRU and CNNs were combined into one architecture in [163], and CNN, BiLSTM, and BiGRU formed a model that could capture short- and long-term patterns [164]. The models consist of deep CNNs developed in [96, 165], CNNs with an attention mechanism in [57, 166], and CNN models inspired by Inception Net and Dense Net architectures in [167]. In [168, 169] the authors explored CNNs with fusion methods at the data, feature, and decision levels. The model in [170] integrates LSTM and residual networks into one architecture to enhance temporal modeling and mitigate optimization issues. In [50], the authors introduced ensemble methods to combine CNN-Net, encoded-net, CNN-LSTM models, and ensemConvNet into a single model.

In [65], the authors proposed merging CNNs with primary and activity/gait capsule layers. A deep RNN with LSTM tailored for edge computing was developed in [66, 171, 172]. The performance of various RNN variants was presented in [14], which demonstrated superior accuracy and faster convergence. In [173], the authors introduced a personalized RNN that memorizes various patterns and temporal variations in a unified memory pool. The capsule network structure developed in [64] modifies the number of convolution layers, kernel size, and inclusion of batch normalization layers. Capsule networks using the LoRa technology encapsulate multiple convolutional layers in parallel [174]. The model developed in [67] integrates capsule and GRU networks with attention mechanisms. An unsupervised deep learning-assisted reconstructed coder fused with a Z-layer scheme was introduced in [175]. The optimization of energy consumption and processing time by leveraging edge computing-assisted GRUs was introduced in [79]. The SETransformer architecture presented in [176] combines transformer-based temporal modeling, squeeze-and-excitation (SE) channel attention, and temporal attention pooling.

All the studies mentioned above used raw input signals, except for those in [168], which employed a 2D spectrogram, and [57], which used a 2D scalogram.

Table 6: WISDM Dataset.

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[39]	RS→2Seq. LSTM→Conv+MP+Conv→GAP+BN+S	TT30:rest/ Adam	HybridLSTM and CNN	Exploration of filter numbers and optimizer types	95.85*
[157]	RS→3Seq.CNN+MP→LSTM→2D+S	user-id /Adam	Hybrid CNN-LSTM	Multiple conv filter sizes	98.04
[77]	RS→4Seq.(Conv1D+MP)→BiLSTM→D+FC+S	TT 70:30 /-	CNN and bidirectional LSTM	Limited exploration of complex or real-time applications	87.62
[158]	Concat.3P(Concat.(3CNN, 2(BiLSTM+MP),LSTM+MP))→SE+BiLSTM+LSTM →F+2Relu+S	- / Adam	Combination of CNNs and RNNs in a deep parallel pipeline structure	A lightweight model incorporating a compact NN module, reducing the overall model size	97.90
[159]	RS→(2 conv1D+MP+DO+S) or (RNN+2DO+S) or (LSTM + 2 DO+S)	TVT / Adam	Simplified, resource-efficient CNNs, RNNs, and LSTMs	Simple architecture and computationally efficient	CNN:98.35, RNN: 98.95, LSTM: 99.06
[160]	RS→Concat3P((Conv1D+Relu+DO+MP+F)→2GRU+DO)→D+BN+S	Train:29, test:7users /Adam	Three-head architecture combining CNN and GRU	A multi-input architecture can capture both deep and shallow features	97.21
[161]	RS→6 Conv1D+AvgP →16 Conv1D+AvgP→3Seq. GRU→F+D+S	K-CV / Adam	Hybrid CNN-GRU	No optimization for resource efficiency on IoT devices	98.21
[162]	RS→Concat.(3P 1DCNN) →2GRU+GAP+BN→S	TT first 30S: rest/Adam	multichannel CNN-GRU	Few model parameters	96.41
[163]	RS→BiGRU+MP→2Seq.(Conv1D+MP)→F+2D+S	TT first 30S: rest/RMSprop	Hybrid BiGRU-CNN	computationally intensive	97.94
[164]	RS→CNN→2Seq.(CNN+MP)+DO→BiLSTM+MP →BiGRU+DO+D+S	TT 80:20 /-	Five hybrid models combining CNN, BiLSTM, and BiGRU with diverse filter sizes in CNN	The model excels in sensitivity, accuracy, and precision	CCBB:99.32, CCGGL:94.03, CGCG:96.33, CBCG:95.62, CCCR:93.8
[96]	RS→4 1DCNN→F+2(D+BN+DO)→D+S	10-CV /5opt: Adam(best)	1D-CNN	Low computational with challenges in recognizing postural transition activities	97.8
[165]	RS→1DCNN→Concat.(1+(IDB+CAS)) →IDB →GAP+FC+S	TT 80:20 / Adam	CNN identity and basic (IDB), and channel and spatial attention (CAS)	Lightweight and low complexity architecture	LSTM: 95.15, RNN:91.8, WISNet:96.4
[166]	RS→Concat.(3 Conv2D+MP)→3 att→D+S	-/-	Integration of CNNs and attention modules	Enhanced FE and selection with high model complexity	95.4*

Continued on next page

Table 6 – continued from previous page					
Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[57]	RS→2D freq-time→4 ((Conv+spatial att)→MP+DO)→F+D+S	- / Adam	Three filters and guided mutation with spatial attention in CNNs	Improved feature selection with low computational overhead	with/out FS 99.38/98.34
[167]	RS→3(InceptionDense + Conv1D)→Conv1D+GAP→S	TVT:70:15:15/Adam&RMSprop	1DCNN inspired by InceptionNet and DenseNet	Difficulty in recognizing less-dynamic activities	95.26
[168]	RS→2D representations → 1D CNN+Fu→ S	5-CV / Adam	CNN with data-, feature, and decision fusion	Tested on dataset in an uncontrolled environment	98.4
[169]	RS→MDCNet→DPNet→AFFM→ S	TT:first 26S :rest/Adam	Multiscale dynamic CNN with distance constraint	Complexity with a weak distance constraint	94.6
[170]	RS→3Res(2CNN)→2LSTM→FC+S	- / SGD	LSTM-CNN with residuals	Performs well in tough scenarios than in simpler ones	ConvLSTM/+Res:94.7/96.3
[50]	RS→P(CNN+Pr, Encoded +Pr, CNN-LSTM+Pr)→ Ensemble	5-CV / Adam	Combination of CNN, Encoded, CNN-LSTM using product rule	Low resource requirements with difficulties in selecting appropriate features	97.2
[65]	RS→ 5 Seq. Conv1D→ primary capsule layer→ Activity/gait capsule+S	TVT:70:15 :15 / -	Combines CNN with CapsNet	Limited by the memory constraints of the system	99.30
[66]	RS→3 LSTM layers→ S	TT 80:20/ Adam	LSTM architecture	Successfully deployed on an Android app	95.78
[171]	RS→2 LSTMs+S	TT 70:30/ Adam	Lightweight RNN with LSTM	Use of static sliding window with low computational costs	95.78
[172]	RS→stacked LSTMs→S	LOSO/ Adam	Use cloud computing for model training	Improve the decision speed for low-power devices	97.03
[14]	RS→LSTM-GRU+DO →D+Sigmoid	- / Adam	Network variants: LSTM ¹ and GRU ²	Comparison(LSTM-GRU ³ , StackLSTM ⁴ , StackGRU ⁵)	99.3 ^{1,2} , 99.6 ³ , 99.5 ^{4,5}
[173]	RS→Conv+LSTM+FC+S	TT:75:25/-	Personalized RNN	Platform independent	96.44
[64]	RS→3CNN+(32 primary + 16 Activity) caps→ S	TT 70:30 / Adam	A capsule network combined with a conv block	Feature visualization using t-SNE	98.21
[174]	RS→Conv→2Seq. capsule →FC+S	TT:75:25/-	Capsule with LoRa	Low power consumption	95.2
[67]	RS→Concat((Conv+ Primary+Digit caps), (2Seq. (GRU+atten.))→ FC + S	TT 75:25 / Adam	Capsule networks and GRU with attention	Low-complexity with balanced real-time performance	CapsNet:95.2, CapsGaNet:96.8
[175]	RS→Encoder+Zlayer+ Decoder→ Classifier	- / -	Coder with a Z-layer scheme	Data analytics during training to reduce computation time	97.5
[79]	RS→4Seq.(Conv+Pool)→2Seq. Inception →F→ GRU→ S	TT 70:30/ Adam(best)	Edge-computing-assisted GRU and O-Inception	Low energy consumption with multiscale data analysis	97.52
[156]	RS→ 4Seq. Conv→MP (Concat(conv3,4)→3Seq. Conv→MP(Concat(conv6,7)→3Seq. Conv→MP (Concat(conv9,10)) → FC+S	TT 70:30/ SGD/ADAM	Ten convolutional blocks and depth concatenation for hierarchical feature fusion.	Resilience to noisy or incomplete sensor data and adaptable to different temporal resolutions (50 ms–2 s).	96.58
[176]	RS→stacked Transformer encoders→SE→temporal attention pooling→ S	TT 80:20/ Adam	SETransformer is a transformer with channel and temporal attention	Stable convergence and strong generalization, but limited to accelerometer data	84.68

10.4 HAR systems evaluated using UCI-HAR dataset

This section reviews recent deep models evaluated on the UCI-HAD dataset and highlights advances in CNN-based architectures, hybrid frameworks, attention mechanisms, and ensemble approaches. Innovations include multiscale feature encoding, cross-channel communication, and attention-based refinements, which demonstrate diverse strategies for enhancing feature representation and classification accuracy. Further details are presented in Table 7.

In [C1], the authors introduced a deep CNN model in [177], whereas in [178] the authors presented a CNN-based multiscale feature encoder using a hierarchical split. In [179] integrates CNN pipelines with an attention sub-module for weakly labeled data. In [180], the authors introduced cross-channel communication to enable interactions among all channels in a graph neural network. The model presented in [181] addresses multiclass windows and employs CNNs to expand and contract networks.

The authors introduced a hierarchical deep LSTM model in [53], a model that combines CNN and LSTM in [37, 103, 182–185], and a model that combines a CNN and BiLSTM in [6, 186]. A hybrid model that combines a CNN with stacked LSTM was introduced in [187]. A CNN-LSTM model incorporating a self-attention module was introduced in [24]. A fuzzy logic-based genetic algorithm was embedded in a deep CNN and LSTM model in [112]. The study in [188] introduced a CNN model with varying kernel dimensions and a BiLSTM to capture features at different resolutions. The authors discussed a deep CNN combined with a GRU in [189] and employed a hierarchical multiresolution CNN in conjunction with a GRU in [190]. The model described in [191] combines BiGRUs with three inception modules, and the one introduced in [192, 193] integrates GRU, LSTM, and CNN into one architecture. In [194], the authors proposed different models of GRU, CNN stacked on GRU, and DNN. The model [195] integrates a CNN with a random forest.

The model in [196] integrates an LSTM with an attention mechanism and a convolutional residual network and refines features using squeeze excitation. In [197], the authors introduced an attention-based multihead framework with lightweight convolutional heads and a squeeze-and-excitation attention module. The authors of [198] introduced a self-attention network and sequential LSTM layers using positional encoding (PE) through self-attention layers. The study by [199] presented triplet cross-dimensional attention with three branches to capture cross-interactions by integrating the attention mechanism into the standard CNN and ResNet models. The model in [200] was inspired by Inception-ResNet and used convolution layers with different kernel sizes and residual connections within the inception modules. Predictions are stacked from multiple DL models (CNN-net, CNN-LSTM-net, ConvLSTM-net, and stacked-LSTM-net), and a blender is trained for the final prediction [82]. The authors of [113] proposed ResCBAR-FusionNet, which combines a 1D-CNN, bidirectional GRU, convolutional block attention module (CBAM), and residual connections.

All the studies mentioned above used raw input signals, except for those in [112], which utilized similar image representations.

Table 7: UCI-HAR Dataset.

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[177]	RS→2(Conv1D+DO)→F+D+2FC+S	10-CV/ Adam	One dimensional CNN	Simple and specific need for patients with limited mobility	95.99
[178]	RS→HS (CNN or ResNet)→D+S	TVT 7:2:1 / Adam	CNN with a hierarchical split (HS)	HS does not support adaptive inference	HS+CNN:96.6, HS+Res:97.28
[179]	RS→3Conv+2seq.(MP+Conv)→MP+FC→3Self-att →FC+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	CNN with attention	Facilitates sensor data annotation	93.41
[180]	RS→3Seq.CNN→C3→FC	5-CV/ Adam	CNN with cross-channel communication (C3)	Interaction of channels with low memory computations	3CNN:96.13, +C3:96.98
[181]	RS→2Seq.(Conv+MP) → 2Seq. UpConv → S	TT 70:30 / Adam	First application of U-Net for HAR	Effective for short-term behaviors and fast processing	0.984
[53]	RS→hierarchical LSTM → S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Hierarchical deep LSTM (H-LSTM)	Preprocessing using smoothing and denoising with FE	91.65
[182]	RS→(CNN+FC)→LSTM(s)+Relu→ S	TT 7352 :2947/-	Hybrid CNN-LSTM	Low model complexity	CNN-LSTM: 92.1
[103]	RS→ 4Seq. Conv+ DO+MP+F→LSTM+DO→FC+S	10-CV, LOSO/ Adam, RMSprop	Hybrid CNN-LSTM with Bayesian optimization	Fine-tuning hyperparameters	2stackLSTM: 97.32, CNN- LSTM: 98.49, Model:99.39
[37]	RS→CNN→ConvDecoder+FC→LSTM →FC+S	5-CV, LOSO/Adam	Combination of CNN, AE, and LSTM	Competitive computational times	98.14
[183]	RS→Conv+MP+FC→LSTM→D+S	TT 70:30 / GD	CNN-LSTM with Gaussian standardization	Lightweight and efficient model	97.89
[184]	RS→CNN→LSTM→D+S	TT 70:30 /Adam	Hybrid CNN and LSTM	Single person and dataset	93.40
[185]	Concat.(STFT→2Seq.(2DCNN+DO)→DO+2D), (RS→3Seq.(LSTM+DO), D))→ S	TVT:rest: S(26:30): S(2,4,9,10, 12,13,18,20, 24)/Adam	Hybrid 2D CNN and LSTM	Balance between model complexity and performance	95.66
[6]	RS→Concat.3P(2-1D CNN)→BiLSTM→D+S	TT 7352: 2947/Adam	Hybrid multibranchs of CNN and BiLSTM	Feature extraction using filters with different sizes	96.37
[186]	RS→BiLSTM→Conv→P+S	TT 7982: 2947 /-	Hybrid BiLSTM and CNN	Handles fine-grained feature extraction	D/BiLSTM: 96.75/95.7
[24]	RS→Concat.(Conv→2(LSTM+Self-att))→LSTM→Concat.2P(2(D+DO))+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Hybrid CNN and LSTM with self-attention	A robust architecture	93.11
[112]	RS→resemble images→FGA+PSOACO→CNN→LSTM→ S	TT 80:20 / PSOACO	Hybrid CNN-LSTM with feature selector FGA-PSOACO	Balanced accuracy and privacy with low computation time and cost	99.92
[188]	RS→2Seq(4P CNN)→FC+DO→(BiLSTM+LSTM+FC+DO)→FC+DO+D+S	TT 70:30/ Adam	Hybrid CNN, LSTM, and BiLSTM with varying kernel sizes	A lightweight architecture confuses in differentiating between similar activities	97.05
[189]	RS→ CNN→ GRU→ S	TT 70:30 / -	CNN and GRU	Monitor rehabilitation exercises	CNN: 95.99, CNNGRU:96.8
[190]	Concat.(RS→(Concat.(3(CNN+D+Relu),CNN)→MP+FC+DO),(Rs→2(GRU+tanh)+FC+DO))→FC+DO+D+Relu→ S	TT 70:30/ RMSprop	Hierarchical multiresolution CNN with GRU	Output visualization using t-SNE with limitation to single-person activity	94.50
[191]	Rs→2BiGRU→3 Inception +GAP→ D+S	TVT:7:2:1 / Adam	Bi-GRU-Inception model	Few model parameters	95.42
[192]	RS→CNN→D+MP+F→GRU→ D+S	TT 70:30 / -	Hybrid CNN, LSTM, and GRU	GRU shows superior performance in recognition	96.83
[193]	Rs→GRU→LSTM→2 Conv1D+MP+2Conv1D → F+ BN +D+ S	TT 7352: 2947Samples/Adam	Hybrid GRU, LSTM, and CNN	Few model parameters with limited focus on complex or unstructured activities	93.43

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Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[194]	RS→ Fused((4 CNN1D +2 (GRU+FC) (feature vector+3DNN))→ FC+S	TT 7352:2947 / Adam	Ensemble learning combines GRU, CNN+GRU, and DNN	Reduces errors between similar activities with real-time monitoring	GRU/+stack CNN:92.5/93.5, ELA:96.8*
[195]	RS→ 2Seq. Conv1D+MP→CNN+MP→F+D→ RF	TT 70:30 / Adam	CNN with random forest (DeepCNN-RF)	Low training time with randomness introduced by RF	CNN/+LSTM:97, +RF:98.2
[196]	RS→Concat.((LSTM(s)+AM+(Conv1D+SE+Res+SE+GAP)) → MLP→ S	TT 7352:2947 samples / Adam	Dual-channel LSTM and conv ResNet with adaptive channel squeeze and pooling	Handles multichannel data efficiently	3LSTM/+Res: 94.8./+AM+Res:95.6./+AM+Res+SE:96.5, Model:97.7
[197]	RS→Fu.3(CNN+SE→CNN +F)→FC+D+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Lightweight Conv1D heads with SE Attention	Low computational costs	Non aTT 94.7 att: 95.4
[198]	RS→ LSTM+PE→ self-att→ GAP+FC+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Self-attention using LSTM	Potential issues with inter-class similarities.	Natt: 94.1, att: 97.1
[199]	RS→2(CNN→3P(att)) →CNN→FC+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	triplet cross-dimensional attention	Low computational cost with good generalization	96.77*
[200]	RS→BN→(Inception+BN+Relu) → Relu+GAP → S	TVT:rest: S(4,12,20): S(2,9,10,13,18,24)/ -	iSPL inception inspired by Inception-ResNet	Expanded without loss of performance that drops when user data is mixed using CV	95.09
[82]	RS→Ensemble(CNN, CNN-LSTM, ConvLSTM, StackedLSTM)→ prediction stacking→ S	TT / Adam	Ensemble of (CNN ¹ , CNN-LSTM ² , ConvLSTM ³ , StackedLSTM ⁴)	Flexible architecture	92.64 ¹ , 93.52 ² , 92.53 ³ , 92.16 ⁴ , Ensemble: 95.05
[187]	RS→2Seq(Conv1D+MP)→2Seq(LSTM→F + 2D→FC+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	CNN-LSTMs hybrid model	Limited to recognizing simultaneous activities	94.44
[113]	RS→2P((Conv1D+MP) +BiGRU+L-Norm)→ L-Norm→CBAM→BiGRU +L-Norm → FC+GA+S	5fold CV / Nadam	Integration of CNN, BiGRU, CBAM, and residual connections	Lightweight design robust to noise and dynamic conditions unverified	97.4

10.5 HAR systems evaluated using OPPORTUNITY dataset

This section reviews deep models evaluated using the OPPORTUNITY dataset. These models integrate CNNs with techniques such as wavelet transforms, LSTMs, BiLSTMs, GRUs, attention mechanisms, and GCNs. The reviewed studies have contributed to performance improvements through enhanced feature representation, attention mechanisms, and learning methods. Further details are presented in Table 8.

The authors introduced a CNN model combined with a wavelet transform in [201], a multilevel CNN architecture and DWT in [202], an adaptive architecture with multi-output CNNs and an output block processor in [203], and shallow CNNs with channel selectivity in [204]. A multibranch CNN with a selective kernel to aggregate receptive and multiscale information was presented in [205]. In [45], the authors introduced a multitask CNN with a selective kernel as the backbone for multiscale window and boundary offset prediction. A deep CNN model incorporating attention layers was developed in [206]. The deep hybrid models developed in [207, 208] combine CNNs and LSTMs in one architecture, and those in [209] integrate CNNs and LSTMs with a squeeze and excitation (SE) module. Deep CNNs and LSTMs with attention modules were integrated into different architectures in [84, 210, 211] and combined with autoencoders in [212]. Resampling and multiclass focal loss strategies were explored in [213], using CNN-LSTMs to address the class distribution and handle minority classes. In [214], the authors employed overlapped windows and a Hamming function with a hybrid model comprising CNNs and LSTMs. A CNN-LSTM with a dense connection and multilayer feature aggregation was proposed in [62].

In [49], the authors introduced a hybrid model that integrates a CNN with a BiLSTM, whereas in [44], the authors proposed combining a BiLSTM with residual connections between stacked cells. CNNs were combined with GRUs in a hybrid model in [215], and inception-like modules with CNNs and GRUs were introduced in [216]. A deep model consisting of a residual CNN and BiGRU was introduced in [217]. In [218], the authors addressed intra-class diversity and similarity using a margin mechanism applicable to four DL networks: MLP, CNN, LSTM, and hybrid CNN-LSTM networks. An asymmetric residual network with two paths of short and long time windows was designed in [219]. In [72], the model combined GCNs and LSTMs in one architecture and GCNs, TCNs, and LSTMs in another architecture [220]. The model in [97] presented a lightweight network using MLPs with gating. A lightweight CNN using Lego filters was introduced in [221], where the filters improved the convolution speed using a split-transform-merge strategy. The study in [222] presented a Bi-GAN+FFT that converts accelerometer data into frequency-domain images for cross-axis learning, refined by a fuzzy inference layer and HMM.

In [223], the authors introduced a multidimensional parallel convolutional network using multidimensional convolutional kernels and multiscale residual squeeze-and-excitation (SE) modules. In [59],

the authors introduced multisource adversarial domain adaptation using a feature extractor, domain discriminator, label classifier, and label decider. A transformer with multihead positional encoding and federated learning (FL) to enhance feature extraction and preserve user data privacy is described in [114].

All the studies mentioned above used raw input signals, except those in [214, 222], which utilized raw data and its FFT, and those in [201, 202], which employed the wavelet transform.

Table 8: OPPORTUNITY Dataset.

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[201]	RS→CWT→2Conv→2Seq.(MP+Conv)+2FC+S	- / -	Wavelet transform combined with CNN	Enhances convergence speed and reduces loss	91.65*
[202]	RS→CNN→Concat. 3P (Conv+MP+ DWT) → D+BN+DO+S	- / Adam	Multilevel residual CNN incorporating 1D DWT	Learns complex patterns in long signals using DWT	93.76
[203]	RS→OBP→2multi-output (Conv1D + Relu) → F+D+S	TVT:(A1:5), DRILLS1: A(S2,3): A1,2, DRILL(S 2,3)/Adam	Adaptive CNN using an output predictor (OBP) to select parts of network during inference	Energy and memory efficiency	91.57
[204]	n (Channel selective CNN ResNet+BN+Relu)→FC	- / SGD	CNN with channel selection	Prioritize important channels for better allocation	CNN:79.67, ResNet:82.36
[205]	RS→CNN→ multiple Seq. (SKConv + BN + Relu)→ FC+S	- / Adam	A multibranch conv with an attention selective kernel	Flexible capturing of multi-scale information with adaptive field sizes	n CNN:90.86, +SE:91.84, +SKconv:93.06
[45]	RS→CNN→2Seq(SKConv+ BN+Relu)→ D+S	- / Adam	MTHARS multitask with a selective kernel	Multi-class windowing with boundary offset prediction	92.13*
[206]	RS→ 4 Conv→ 2 att→ S	TVT A(S1),A1:3(S2,3):A4,5(S2,3)/GD	CNN with attention	Fast processing with accuracy improvement	gestures:92.8*, locomotion: 90.6*
[207]	RS→2LSTM→Conv+MP+ Conv +GAP→ BN+D+S	TT rest: A4,5(S2,3)/ Adam	Hybrid CNN-LSTM	CNN and LSTM structures with minor modifications	92.63*
[208]	RS→2CNNs→LSTM+2D +S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Hybrid CNN-LSTM	There is still a room for improvement	95.2
[209]	RS→ 3Seq. Group Conv →SE→ Group Conv→ 2Seq. LSTM→ FC+ S	TT rest (except(A5-S1)):A4,5-S2,3/Adam	Deep CNN-LSTM with squeeze and excitation (SE)) and group convolutions	Low computational complexity (FLOPs) by 88.93	90.80
[84]	RS→CNN→Self-att→ LSTM→ S	- / Adam	RAN, simultaneously infers many activities	Reduces the burden of manual data labeling	78.6
[210]	RS→1DCNN+SE+Relu →LSTM+Self att+SL+ S → SL + FC	TT rest: S1-3 (runs2,4,5) /Adam	CNNs, LSTM, and self-attention combined with sparse learning (SL)	Accommodate new classes with efficient handling of weaker and stronger nodes	with/out: 95.21/96.50
[211]	RS→4Seq.(Conv+CBAM) → 2 LSTM → FC+S	TVT 60:20:20, 5-CV/ Adam	Convolutional block attention module (CBAM) on deep CNN-LSTMs	Attention mechanism does not increase the number of model parameter	with/out CBAM: 0.74*/0.77*
[212]	RS→Stack(LSTMs, CNN-LSTM, Encoder-Decoder) →FC+S	TVT rest: A2(S1):S2, 3(A4,5)/ Adam	Learns 3 features: statistical, temporal, and spatial	The integration of multiple feature types may complicate the model architecture	maF86.01
[213]	RS→ 4Seq. Conv1D→ LSTM → DO	TVT rest: S1(A5):S2, 3(A4,5)/ focal loss	CNN-LSTM with multi-class focal loss	Handles imbalanced datasets where multi-class focal loss lowers performance	91.00
[214]	RS/FFT→2Seq. Conv2D → 2LSTM→D+S	4-CV/ RMSprop	Hybrid CNNs and LSTMs for repetitive movements and postures	Requires separate tuning for each movement	non-repetitive:66.91, postures:95.92
[62]	RS→MFAM(DCM(3(Conv +Relu))→Fu→2LSTM+FC	TT Rest: S2,3(A4,5)/ Adadelta	CCN-LSTM with multi-layer feature aggregation	Feature fusion of multimodal data with few parameters	0.922 [§]
[49]	RS→3Seq. (Conv1D+AF +DO+MP)→ FC+2D+S	TT 80:20 / Adam	1DCNN with four activation functions (AF)	Evaluation of 5 datasets and SelU AF is the best	DNN:95.96, C1DCNN:99.4
[44]	RS→Res(ReLu+2Seq. (BiLSTM+ReLU)+BN) →D+S	TT rest: S2,3(R4,5) / Adam	BiLSTM with residual connections	Manual adjustment of model parameters	90.5
[215]	RS→ 3 stacked Conv1D → F→ 2 GRU+2 D+S	- / Adam	Hybrid CNN-GRU	Identifies a wide range of actions	94.87
[216]	RS→Concat.3(P(Conv, 4Conv, (MP+Conv)))+ MP → 2GRU→ FC+S	- / -	Combines inception and GRU with multiscale conv kernels	Low misidentification and interference tested on the minnow turbot dual core board	94.6
[217]	RS→ Concat. n Seq. (Conv1D + Res)→BiGRU → FC + S	TT rest: S1(A2),S2 (A3),S3-A4/Adam	hybrid RCNN-BiGRU with swarm intelligence (MPA variants)	Low complexity with improvement in using unlabeled data	88.83

Continued on next page

Ref.	Model	VP/Opt	Innovation	Specialty	Accuracy
[218]	RS→(MLP CNN LSTM CNN-LSTM)→margin-based→S	TT S(1:4, A1-3) & Drills:A4,5 /Adadelta	A margin mechanism to four networks	Improves intra-class compactness and inter-class separation	MLPM:91.28, CNNM:90.88, LSMM:92.30, HybridM:91.9
[219]	RS→CNN→Res→FC+S	-/ GD Adadelta	An asymmetric residual network	Lightweight with low computational complexity	90.29 [§]
[72]	RS→Concat. P-CNNs→avg. 3 GCN→LSTM→FC+S	TVT:rest:S1 -A2:S2,3 (A4,5)/Adam	Multigraph conv using topic model and division-based representations	Low computational complexity with scalability limited for dynamic activities	0.883
[220]	RS→2Seq.(GCN+TCN)→2Seq. TCN→LST→S	TVT 3:1:1 / Adam	Graph temporal convolution, and LSTM	Captures dynamics and non-linearity in sensors and time	92.58 [*]
[97]	RS→MLPs→FC+S	S1-A,S2,3 (A1,2):S2,3(A3) :S2,3(A4,5) /AdamW	All MLP architecture of non-overlapping patches	All computations involve matrix multiplications and optimizing compatibility	CNNs: 90.52, all-MLP: 91.11
[221]	RS→CNN→2Seq.(light CNN)→FC+S	TT 70:30 / Adam	Lightweight CNN using LEGO filters	Low FLOPS effective for mobile applications	88.09
[223]	RS→Reshape→P(1D, 2D, 3D)MRCSE→F+FC+DO→Relu+FC+DO+S	10-CV / -	Parallel CNNs with multiscale residual convolutional SE modules	Hardware efficient with large memory footprint	95.42 [†]
[59]	RS→3 Conv2D→N discriminators → N classifiers →Label decider	TVT 60:20:20 / Adam	MSADA and a perplexity score to map the most pertinent source domains	Effectively handles cross-domain discrepancies	82
[222]	RS→FFT→BiGAN→CNN→FC+fuzzy S→HMM	round-robin fashion CV / -	Bi-directional GAN with fuzzy inference and HMM post-processing	Data augmentation Bi-GAN and HMM, but sensitive to synthetic data volume	86.8
[114]	RS→Transformer→F+D+S	-/Adam	Transformer with federated learning	Privacy-preserving training with high computations	99.79

10.6 Performance of reviewed HAR systems on other datasets

Table 9 presents the performance metrics of the reviewed HAR systems on datasets other than the reference dataset. Based on these results, the total number of articles reviewed for each dataset was USD-HAR (30), PAMAP2 (73), WISDM (66), UCI-HAD (72), and OPPORTUNITY (56). It is important to note that there may be variations in the experimental protocols and modeling parameters, such as batch size, training epochs, learning rate, window size, and overlap, for other datasets. These variations influence performance and can lead to discrepancies in benchmarking between studies.

Table 9: Results of related work on other datasets.

Dataset	Results
PAMAP2	[42] CNN/+HC:89.4/90.9, ResNet/+HC:91.6/92.97 [120] (LOSO): 96 [†] , 96 [†] (test subject) [119] 81.1 [*] [162] 96.25 [158] 98.52 [121] CSNet:88.43, TCCSNet:89.10 [104] base: 90.08, filter prune:91.45, Gauss noise:92.25, in/External activation:91.79/92.18 [63] Transformer:97, ConvTransformer:99 [128] Base/Proposed:90.23/92.14 [123] 97.7 [82] CNN:97, CNNLSTM:96.9, ConvLSTM:96.88, StackedLSTM:95.96, Ensem-HAR:97.73 [164] CCBB:96.1 [211] DeepConvLSTM/+ CBAM att:95 [*] /96 [*] [115] 98.04 [57] with/out FS: 98.29/97.55 [216] 94 [86] Linear Conv Grouped/+ CNN:91.46, /+ ResNet:91.5 [130] DNN/+AAE:69.5/92.8, RNN/+AAE:82.1/96.3, CNN/+AAE: 81.1/98.8 [116] CNN: 92.63, GRU:94.40, BiLSTM:93.41, LSTM:92.56, DBN:85.08 [97] CNNs:91.26, all-MLP:92.13 [124] 98 [†] [178] SVM:95.35, CNN:96.41, HS-CNN:97.76, ResNet:97.89, HS-ResNet: 99.02 [181] U-Net:97 [90] DCNN Ensemble:89.01, MDE+HC:86.9 [210] without sparse learning:98.47, with sparse learning:98.90 [134] 99.60 [60] 99.98 [139] 89.43 [143] CNN:97.11, CNN-GRU:97.32, CNN-LSTM:99.89 [112] CNN-GRU:97.21, DCNN-LSTM:99.94 [12] 97.32 [180] 3-layers CNN/+C3/+90.23/91.93, 6-layers CNN:91.11 [217] 94.06 [96] 90.24 [221] 92.97 [90]m DCNN Ensemble:83.99, Multimodal: 79.62, MDE:79.76, MDE: 81.25,83.75, MDE+HC: 73.36 [178] CNN:91.35, HS-CNN:92.57, Res:92.77, HS-Res:93.75 [49] DNN:81.04, BDLSTM: 91.2, CNN(Swish):94.2 [205] Base/+SE:91.21/92.68, Base+ SK Conv:93.54 [199] CNN/+TA:91.1/92.5, Equally-sized Res/+TA:92.6 [*] /93.2 [*] [212] miF:93.23, maF:93.38 [223] avg FW:98.33 [71] 98.36 [45] 0.948 [126] 0.983 [112] CNN-GRU:95.27, DCNN-LSTM:99.86 [204] CNN/+SelectConv:90.57/91.46, ResNet/+SelectConv:91.53/94.33 [6] 94.29 [37] 94.33 [118] 97.8 [218] MLP-M:82.47, CNN-M:93.74, LSM-M:86.00, Hybrid-M 93.52, CNN:91.46, ResNet:91.50 [100] 99 [†] [68] 91 [†] [187] 99.86 [114] 99.52
WISDM	[56] Proposed: 90.41, baseline CNN-LSTM: 89.83 [147] 99.12 [*] [207] 95.85 [*] [40] CNN/ +DFC 97.61/98.3, ResNet/ +DFC: 97.85/99.21 [6] 96.05 [118] 98.48 [104] Base:97.08, Filter prune: 97.32, Gauss noise: 99.13, In/External activation: 98.32/99.02 [128] Baseline , Proposed 97.21, 99.04 [121] CSNet: 91.21, TCCSNet: 92.51 [122] 99.02 [82] CNN: 96.62, CNNLSTM: 97.84, ConvLSTM: 97.33, StackedLSTM-net 98.61, Ensem-HAR: 98.7 [86] CNN: 98.75, ResNet: 99.12 [126] 0.99 [202] 99.35 [188] 98.53 [196] 98.90 [191] 98.25 [192] CNN: 93.17, Hybrid CNN-LSTM: 93.83, CNN-LSTM-Dense 94.17, LSTM: 93, StackedLSTM: 94.33, BiLSTM 95.33, ResBiLSTM 92.5, GRU:98 [195] DNN:74, DNN + LSTM 81, DNN + GRU 80, CNN: 88, CNN + LSTM 94, CNN + GRU 82, CNN + RF 97.77 [37] CNN: 93.27, LSTM:88.34, AE: 90.08, CNN-LSTM 92.78, Conv AE 91.97, ConvAE-LSTM 98.67 [197] NonAtt /Proposed:0.982/0.976 [137] Traditional/Cascade: 99.34/99.92 [16] 97.3 [204] CNN: 97.01, CNN+SelectConv 97.44, ResNet 98.22, ResNet + SelectConv 98.52 [205] Base: 96.83, Base+ SE blocks: 97.42, Base+ SK conv: 98.13 [199] Standard CN/ +TA: 96.73 [*] /97.34 [*] , Equally-sized ResNet/ +TA: 98.10/98.61 [155] 95.83 [222] 99.12

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Table 9 – continued from previous page

Dataset	Results
UCI	[42] CNN/+HC:95.6/96.2, ResNet/+HC:95.65/97.01 [146] DWCNN-noCWT 90.56 [†] , DWCNN-noRAB 94.18 [†] , <i>DWCNN</i> : 99.56 [†] [160] 96.20 [118] 97.5 [104] Base: 95.89, Filter prune: 96.67, Gauss noise: 97.23, In/External activation 96.84/97.18 [48] 2-Stage 98.63, M-Stage 99.29 [15] 91.04 [*] [25] CNN 0.90, Hybrid 0.90 [205] Base: 96.11, Base+ SE blocks: 96.60, Base+ SK conv:97.21 [221] 96.9 [45] 97.23 [*] [202] 96.13 [215] 98.74 [116] CNN: 98.74, GRU: 98.21, biLSTM: 97.66, LSTM: 96.41, DBN: 93.49 [139] 99.03 [16] 98.6 [86] Linear Conv Grouped/+ CNN: 94.16, + ResNet: 95.04, [128] Base/Proposed: 96.23/97.35 [64] 95.28 [162] 96.67 [89] 97.25 [130] DNN/+AEE:97.5/ 99.3, RNN/+AEE: 86.1/99.3, CNN/+AEE: 98.2/99.4 [212] miF 90.53 maF 90.58 [44] 93.6 [147] 96.3 [*] [210] with/out sparse learning 98.09/97.8 [87] 97.43 [161] 96.776 [65] 97.92 [127] CNN 90.322, LSTM 90.278, CNN-LSTM 90.356, CNN-LSTM 91.235, ODL-HAR proposed 93.00 [144] CNN 92.71, LSTM 89.01, BLSTM 89.40, MLP 86.83, SVM 90.5 [137] Traditional learning 96.17, Cascade learning 96.84 [57] with/out FS: 99.45/98.74 [49] CNN (Swish Activation) 99.58, CNN(ELU) 99.45 [136] CNN-Rep 97.25, CNN-RepV1 97.9 [143] CNN: 95.56, CNN+GRU 97.79, CNN+LSTM 96.78 [163] 96.15 [77] 90.57 [207] 95.78 [*] [204] CNN/+ SelectConv: 96.12/96.77, ResNet/+ SelectConv: 96.33/97.28 [14] LSTM 97.5, GRU 97.4, LSTM-GRU 98.1, Stacked LSTM 98.3, Stacked GRU 98.4 [135] Base: 0.96, Pred 0.95, Sim 0.96, Predsim 0.97 [132] 87.89 [*] 1001[125]98.641001[156]97.87
Opportunity	[42] CNN/+HC:90.19/91, ResNet/+HC:91.1/91.55 [120] (LOSO): 42 [†] , 67 [†] (test subject) [40] CNN/ +DFC: 77.61/80.22, ResNet/ +DFC: 80.38/82.91 [104] Base:78.97, Filter prune: 79.85, Gauss noise: 81.42, In/External activation: 80/81.36 [63] Transformer: 84, ConvTransformer 86 [128] Base/Proposed: 90.01/93.82 [153] CNN: 79.01, ResNet: 81.18, Predsim CNN: 79.29, Pred ResNet: 80.67, Sim ResNet: 82.42, Predsim ResNet: 83.06 [145] CNN 77.53, Att-based CNN 80.42, Residual: 82.05, Att-based Residual 82.75 [124] 69 [†] [116] CNN: 92.44, GRU:92.02, biLSTM: 90.59, LSTM:88.79, DBN:87.13 [131] 89.31 [115] 88.85 [100] 68 [†] [86] Linear Conv Grouped/ + CNN: 78.78, + ResNet: 81.54 [68] 68 [†] [138] With/out post-processing Soft-max: 77.5/70.88, Fuzzy Soft-max: 85.1/78 [148] CNN base: 79.91, CNN BiGRU-ATT: 84.33, Multi-ResAtt (NoRNN+NoAtt): 84.83, Multi-ResAtt (BiRNN+Att): 85.4, Multi-ResAtt (BiLSTM+Att): 85.08, Multi-ResAtt (BiGRU+NoAtt): 86.86, Multi-ResAtt: 87.82 [135] Base: 0.7685, Pred 0.7994, Sim 0.7997, Predsim 0.8100 [152] Locomotion 75.83, Gestures 80.2 [123] 87.73 [37] 95.69 [147] 90.1 [*] [137] Traditional/ Cascade: 97.51/99.1 [136] CNN-Rep 81.33, CNN-RepV1 80.93 [134] CondConv 81.18, DeepCond/convLSTM 92.96 [180] 3 layers CNN (base) 77.86, base+C3:80.23, base+C3 (5-CV) 80.14, 6 layers CNN:79.59

11 Discussion

It can be asserted that no model is perfect for any given situation. The selection of an optimal model for HAR depends on various factors, including problem complexity, dataset size, annotation availability, data quality, computing resources, training time, and performance, which must align with specific application requirements and data characteristics. For a fair comparison, it is essential to address identical parameters, validation procedures, and splitting protocols. Reducing the time complexity of a classification model often results in decreased accuracy, whereas achieving good accuracy can result in an unacceptable time complexity [224]. Traditional ML and manual feature engineering may suffice for simple tasks and eliminate the need for DL. If the dataset is small, DL models may overfit; therefore, using a shallow network or data augmentation methods, such as GANs, can help. Semi-supervised learning is a viable option for large unlabeled datasets. Data quality also influences model design; noisy sensor data may require denoising structures, such as autoencoders and deeper models, to enhance noise resilience.

The relationships and usage frequencies of different DL models and combinations in the research context are shown in Figure 8. The stacked column indicates the model used alone and in combination with other models as a hybrid architecture. The foundation of the model is formed by core architectural families, each with distinct inductive biases. The CNN family, including advanced variants such as ResNet and CNN+Res, excels at capturing local, translation-invariant patterns through convolutional filters, making them powerful for grid-like data such as images and time series. In parallel, the RNN family, encompassing fundamental RNNs, LSTMs, and GRUs, is specialized for sequential data by maintaining a hidden state that propagates information through time, with bidirectional variants such as BiLSTM and BiGRU designed to capture contextual information from both the past and future.

The figure illustrates several hybrid architectures that combine the strengths of these foundational families, reflecting the trend toward more powerful and specialized models. Models, such as CNN+LSTM and LSTM+GCN, typically leverage a CNN for local feature extraction, with its output fed into a recurrent layer, such as an LSTM, to model long-range temporal dependencies. The LSTM+GCN variant specifically integrates a GCN to handle complex graph-structured data. Another significant category includes modern attention-based architectures; the most notable of which is the transformer, a dominant paradigm that relies entirely on self-attention mechanisms. The related attention mechanism (AM) is also featured and is often used as a component to enhance other models by allowing them to dynamically focus on the most relevant parts of the input sequence. Capsule networks propose an alternative to CNNs, aiming to better model hierarchical relationships and spatial pose information between features. Autoencoders (AE) are a class of unsupervised models designed for efficient data encoding and

Figure 8: Accumulated use of different networks and their hybrid architecture employed to develop deep learning models for HAR.

reconstruction. Broader architectural classes, such as temporal convolutional networks (TCN), provide a compelling alternative to RNNs for sequence modeling using causal convolutions.

CNNs exhibit competitive performance compared to GRU networks, outperforming biLSTM, LSTM, and DBN models, and are the least memory-demanding architecture [116]. Research on one-dimensional CNNs has demonstrated their superior effectiveness in addressing HAR [103]. CNNs and RNNs, which incorporate local dependencies, are better suited for HAR than fully connected models, such as DBNs, because sensor-based activity recognition involves time-series data, in which temporal information must be directly integrated into the input, thereby negating the need for extensive feature engineering [116]. They exhibit top-tier performance in HAR tasks; however, the optimal choice between them remains uncertain because of potential architectural complexities and resource demands, which require further investigation of their comparative effectiveness and efficiency [116]. Newer architectures, such as transformers and GNNs, are gaining traction, indicating a shift towards more advanced models for HAR tasks.

Before adopting a deep learning approach, it is essential to verify that the dataset size is sufficient to support such methods. Insufficiently labeled data often yield unsatisfactory results due to overfitting and compromised generalizability. In such cases, alternatives, such as shallow neural networks or traditional machine learning approaches, should be considered. Additionally, employing data augmentation techniques can optimize the utilization of available data [19]. Effective data preprocessing and segmentation are essential for enhancing sensor data quality and ensuring accurate activity recognition. Techniques such as denoising, data segmentation, and transformation must be carefully selected and tailored to the type of sensor data to optimize performance and minimize misclassification.

Figure 9 presents the statistics of the frequently used optimizers and validation protocols employed in the revised studies. Adam is generally favored as the most effective optimizer for training deep networks, owing to its stable gradient descent and superior fitting performance. Although other optimizers, such as RMSprop, Adadelta, and SGD, are also used, the balance of efficiency and adaptability makes Adam the preferred choice in several studies. In contrast, the analysis of data partitioning revealed a preference for simple percentage splits, such as 70 – 30 and 80 – 20, highlighting their ease of implementation. Techniques such as the K-fold and LOSO approaches are also commonly used, emphasizing the need for robust validation that accounts for individual variability and enhances generalization to new users. The overall trend indicates a balance between practical efficiency and the need for accurate HAR.

11.1 Practical implications for system designers

To maximize the relevance of this review to practitioners, we synthesized the key findings into a decision matrix for HAR system development:

Figure 9: Analysis of the frequent uses of optimizers and validation protocols.

- For resource-constrained devices (e.g., smartwatches), our analysis indicates that 1D-CNNs offer the best trade-off between accuracy and memory footprint [116]. Researchers should prioritize lightweight architectures over complex transformers unless cloud offloading is available.
- For high-accuracy healthcare monitoring: Hybrid CNN-LSTM models consistently outperform single-architecture models across all five datasets [60, 112]. We recommend employing Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) validation to ensure robustness against inter-subject variability, which is critical for clinical applications.
- For data-scarce environments: When labeled data is limited, our review highlights the efficacy of transfer learning and data augmentation via GANs [194]. Practitioners should avoid deep architectures from scratch in favor of pre-trained models fine-tuned on specific sensory data.
- Optimizer Selection: Regardless of architecture, the Adam optimizer remains the most stable choice for convergence [39, 79], reducing the need for extensive hyperparameter tuning during deployment. These guidelines directly address the relevance gap by converting academic metrics into engineering specifications.”

12 Challenges and Future Research Directions

The development of robust HAR systems that leverage deep learning is a multifaceted endeavor hampered by a series of interconnected challenges that span the entire pipeline, from data collection to real-world deployment. Although deep learning offers superior accuracy, its practical application is constrained by critical issues, including data quality, hardware limitations, model generalization, and privacy, all of which must be systematically addressed to enable effective deployment in real-world settings.

12.1 Data quality and acquisition

High-quality data form the foundation of a robust HAR system. However, acquiring such data involves multifaceted challenges, including hardware configuration, signal integrity, and annotation fidelity. Critical design choices, such as selecting sensor types (e.g., accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers), determining their number and placement on the body (e.g., wrist, chest, and ankle), and ensuring consistent orientation, profoundly influence the discriminative power of the captured signals [225]. These decisions are further complicated by low-level signal imperfections, including gyroscope drift and motion-induced artifacts in accelerometer readings. Even after collection, sensor data are rarely pristine; they commonly suffer from environmental noise, intersubject variability, and missing values caused by transmission failures or hardware malfunctions. The reliability of ground-truth labels is also a concern, as supervised learning depends on annotations that may be inconsistent due to subjective human judgment. Together, these issues shift the primary burden of HAR performance away from the model architecture and toward sophisticated, often domain-specific, pipelines for preprocessing, cleaning, and feature engineering [19, 226].

To address these data-centric challenges, future HAR research must prioritize data efficiency, robustness, and generalization. First, self-supervised and weakly supervised learning, including contrastive learning and masked signal modeling, can drastically reduce reliance on costly manual annotations by extracting meaningful representations from unlabeled sensor streams. Second, robust sensor fusion and calibration-aware architectures should be developed to accommodate the variability in sensor placement, orientation, and hardware across users and devices, thereby minimizing performance degradation in heterogeneous settings. Third, models must be designed to natively handle noise and missing data using probabilistic modeling, attention mechanisms with uncertainty estimation, or generative imputation techniques. To improve cross-subject and cross-dataset generalization, domain adaptation and meta-learning approaches can be used to enable knowledge transfer across populations. Semi-automated annotation pipelines that fuse multimodal cues or incorporate active learning can produce labels that are more accurate and consistent. Additionally, adaptive sensing strategies that dynamically adjust modality selection or sampling rate based on context can reduce power consumption and data volume while preserving recognition accuracy.

12.2 Modeling limitations

The fundamental challenge for deep neural networks in HAR is the intrinsic complexity of human movement. This creates a dual problem: high intra-class diversity, in which a single activity, such as “sitting,” can take many forms, and high inter-class similarity, in which distinct actions, such as “walking” and “jogging,” produce nearly identical sensor data. This ambiguity requires feature representations that are more discriminative than those induced by standard classification losses [218]. During deployment, HAR systems inevitably encounter activities that are not observed during training. A closed-set model may confidently misclassify a novel action, such as “rope-jumping,” as a known class, such as “jogging,” thereby leading to critical errors. A further foundational issue is the need to recognize activities from continuous, unlabeled sensor streams [4]. Real-world scenarios lack predefined activity boundaries, and systems must simultaneously perform temporal segmentation (detecting the start and end times). This is commonly cast as a multi-label temporal classification task, complicated by sensor noise, real-time processing, and the prevalence of overlapping or concurrent activities (e.g., “walking” while “talking on the phone”).

Future studies should be conducted along several interconnected axes to overcome these modeling limitations. First, discriminative representation learning should be enhanced using contrastive frameworks that explicitly account for intra- and inter-class variations and proximities. Methods, such as prototypical networks, triplet loss with hard negative mining, and hierarchical metric learning, can shape structured embedding spaces in which semantically similar activities remain distinguishable. Second, HAR systems must incorporate robust open-set recognition, including uncertainty-aware classifiers based on Bayesian neural networks, energy-based models, and deep ensembles. Coupled with continual learning strategies, such systems can incrementally integrate new activities without experiencing catastrophic forgetting, thereby enabling long-term adaptability in evolving environments. Third, end-to-end architectures for online temporal segmentation and classification require further innovation. Transformer-based sequence models, temporal convolutional networks with boundary-aware losses, and hybrid state-space approaches offer promising paths for jointly detecting activity boundaries and labeling streaming data. These models should explicitly support overlapping and concurrent activities using multi-label learning formulations.

12.3 Complex activity recognition

A key limitation of current HAR systems is their focus on single-user scenarios; most models and benchmark datasets assume isolated individuals and ignore the contextual dynamics of collaborative interactions. Consequently, recognizing group behaviors, such as coordinated movements in team sports, queuing patterns in public spaces, and conversational turn-taking, remains highly challenging [18]. These activities are not simply the sum of individual actions. Instead, they arise from complex relationships that depend on how elements interact over space and time, something that current models struggle to capture effectively. Equally challenging is the recognition of extended, composite activities, often termed macro-activities, such as “preparing a meal” or “assembling furniture.” Accurate identification requires more than the detection of constituent subactions (e.g., “chopping,” “simmering”). This requires an understanding of their hierarchical organization, logical sequencing, and goal-directed contexts. Models must distinguish between semantically similar but functionally distinct actions (e.g., “chopping vegetables” vs. “chopping wood”) and maintain long-range contextual awareness to infer overarching intent.

Unlike controlled laboratory conditions, the continuous deployment of subject systems leads to sensor degradation, calibration drift, intermittent disconnections, and hardware failure.

To bridge this gap, future work must advance along three interrelated fronts: modeling contextual dynamics, capturing hierarchical activity structures, and ensuring resilience under sensor uncertainty. First, multiagent activity recognition requires architectures that encode relational and spatiotemporal interactions among individuals. Graph neural networks offer a strong foundation, particularly when augmented with attention mechanisms that adapt to varying group sizes and compositions. Progress hinges on new datasets that provide synchronized multiuser sensor streams paired with annotations of collective intent (e.g., “team huddles,” “collaborative assemblies”). Second, recognizing procedural or goal-oriented activities requires hierarchical modeling frameworks that operate across multiple temporal scales. Approaches such as hierarchical temporal memory or neural-symbolic systems with latent program induction can jointly infer subactivity sequences and their higher-level goals. Integrating common-sense knowledge through task ontologies can further disambiguate contextually similar actions through reasoning regarding object affordances and environmental constraints. Finally, HAR systems must include real-time anomaly detection based on reconstruction errors or cross-modal consistency to detect sensor degradation.

12.4 Hardware and computational bottlenecks

The mismatch between the model complexity and stringent limitations of edge hardware fundamentally constrains the real-world deployment of deep learning for HAR. Modern deep architectures, particularly standard CNNs, require substantial computational resources and memory bandwidth, which are often incompatible with resource-constrained devices such as smartwatches and smartphones, where energy efficiency and low latency are critical [27]. Although CNNs effectively capture spatiotemporal patterns, their reliance on sliding-window convolutions and dense tensor operations results in high processing overhead, often exceeding the thermal and power budgets of embedded platforms [86]. Edge-based HAR systems must first expend scarce computational resources on denoising and preprocessing inherently noisy raw sensor streams. They then perform complex inferences on the cleaned data, further straining the processors and memory. The cumulative impacts include excessive latency, rapid battery drain, and degraded user experience, all of which compromise the viability of continuous real-time activity recognition.

Overcoming this hardware–model gap requires a shift toward algorithm–hardware co-design and efficiency-aware learning paradigms that jointly optimize accuracy, energy, and latency. First, a hardware-aware neural architecture search should be employed to automatically discover compact and low-latency models tailored to specific sensor modalities and target-edge platforms. These architectures can simultaneously optimize the accuracy, energy consumption, memory footprint, and inference speed. Second, dynamic and sparse computation strategies enable adaptive efficiency. Models that activate only context-relevant subnetworks via input-dependent gating or conditional execution can significantly reduce computation during periods of low activity. Third, techniques such as federated learning, continual learning with replay buffers, and quantization-aware fine-tuning allow models to evolve with individual users and changing behaviors while respecting strict power and memory limitations. Finally, the field must embrace cross-layer optimization by integrating signal processing, feature extraction, and inference into unified lightweight pipelines. Replacing conventional preprocessing steps (e.g., filtering and segmentation) with differentiable and learnable modules enables end-to-end training and eliminates redundant operations.

12.5 Model generalization and complexity

A central obstacle to deploying HAR systems in real-world settings is the limited generalizability and robustness of current models. Although current algorithms achieve high accuracy on laboratory datasets, they often suffer from significant performance degradation when exposed to uncontrolled variability in real-world environments. This drop stems from multiple sources of domain shifts, including diverse user demographics, heterogeneous hardware specifications, and unconstrained behavioral outliers [210]. These discrepancies reveal a critical gap between controlled benchmarks and their real-world applicability. Although modern systems can detect simple, atomic actions such as “walking” or “sitting,” they struggle with high-level, composite tasks such as “cooking a meal” or “assembling furniture.” The identification of such macro-activities requires the precise detection of constituent sub-actions and an understanding of their hierarchical structures. Multimodal learning, which integrates signals from accelerometers, gyroscopes, microphones, and other sensors, offers a path toward greater robustness and richer contextual

understanding [30]. However, effectively fusing heterogeneous, asynchronous, and potentially incomplete data streams remains challenging. Current fusion strategies often fail to leverage modality-specific strengths, limiting their ability to distinguish fine-grained activities such as “jogging” and “running.”

To develop robust HAR systems that can interpret high-level human behavior under diverse real-world conditions, future research should focus on three interconnected aspects: domain-invariant representation learning, hierarchical activity understanding, and adaptive multimodal fusion. To address domain shifts, techniques such as adversarial feature alignment and self-supervised pre-training on unlabeled data can encourage models to learn representations that are invariant to users, devices, or sensor placement. To model semantically complex activities, neural-symbolic models that combine deep learning with hierarchical recurrent networks can jointly infer subaction sequences and their overarching intent. Incorporating external knowledge, such as activity task graphs, may further enable the few-shot recognition of unseen composite tasks. Finally, multimodal fusion must evolve beyond static or late fusion using adaptive strategies. Dynamic mechanisms, such as attention-based modality weighting, cross-modal transformers, and uncertainty-guided gating, can selectively trust sensor streams based on real-time signal quality and contextual relevance. Training with modality dropout and noise injection can further improve resilience to missing or corrupted inputs, paving the way for robust context-aware HAR systems.

12.6 Data privacy and security risks

The pervasive, continuous, and real-time collection of sensor data in HAR systems introduces a significant privacy risk. Beyond basic motion patterns, these systems often capture highly sensitive information, including fine-grained location traces, behavioral biometrics, physiological signals, and detailed daily routines, thereby constructing an intimate digital profile of the user. When stored in centralized repositories, this rich data becomes a high-value target for cyberattacks, creating a single point of failure that can lead to large-scale breaches with serious consequences, such as surveillance, discrimination, or identity theft. Moreover, existing HAR systems lack mechanisms to enforce user control over data access, and most benchmark datasets and models assume closed, static environments that ignore real-world complexities, such as open-set recognition and sensor unreliability. Current evaluation practices also neglect critical dimensions such as privacy leakage, energy consumption, and latency in decentralized settings, hindering the development of systems that are both accurate and ethically sound.

Future research on HAR must treat privacy as a foundational design principle rather than an optional add-on. A critical priority is the development of lightweight decentralized architectures that are viable for resource-constrained wearables and internet of things (IoT) devices. Current blockchain implementations often incur excessive storage, computational, and energy costs, thus limiting their applicability in real-world scenarios. Promising directions include permissioned ledgers, sharding, and hybrid models that store sensor data off-chain while recording only immutable cryptographic hashes on-chain. Techniques such as differential privacy can be used to perturb model updates in federated learning settings, whereas homomorphic encryption enables secure computation directly on encrypted sensor data. Zero-knowledge proofs further empower users to verify activity-based claims without revealing any raw behavioral information, thus striking a balance between the utility and confidentiality of the data. User-centric data sovereignty must also be operationalized through intelligent and dynamic consent mechanisms. Smart contracts should move beyond static access rules to support context-aware, fine-grained policies that users can audit and revoke at their discretion.

13 Conclusion

This survey provides a systematic and dataset-centric review of deep learning models for human activity recognition (HAR), with a focused analysis of five widely adopted benchmark datasets: USC-HAD, PAMAP2, WISDM, UCI-HAR, and OPPORTUNITY. By placing datasets at the forefront of the analysis, this study offers a unique perspective that facilitates clear comparisons across methods and highlights dataset-specific trends, limitations, and opportunities for future research.

This review synthesizes 226 studies, offering a structured taxonomy of HAR systems, a comparative analysis of various deep learning architectures, and an in-depth evaluation of preprocessing, feature extraction, optimizers, validation protocols, and performance metrics. The key findings indicate that hybrid models, particularly those that combine convolutional neural networks with recurrent neural networks or attention mechanisms, consistently achieve high recognition accuracy by leveraging both spatial and temporal dependencies in sensor data. Among optimizers, Adam is widely preferred for

its stability and efficiency, whereas validation protocols, such as leave-one-subject-out and K-fold cross-validation, ensure model generalizability across users.

Despite these advancements, significant challenges remain, including sensor noise, intersubject variability, class imbalance, real-time processing constraints, and privacy concerns. Future research should prioritize the development of robust, efficient, and generalizable models that can be used in real-world settings. Promising directions include self-supervised and contrastive learning for reduced annotation dependency, domain adaptation for cross-user and cross-device generalization, lightweight architectures for edge deployment, and privacy-preserving techniques such as federated learning and differential privacy.

By addressing these challenges and leveraging emerging technologies, the next generation of HAR systems can achieve greater accuracy, efficiency, and usability, paving the way for broader adoption in healthcare, smart environments, and personalized assistive technologies.

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